

European Research Infrastructure supporting Smart Grid and Smart Energy Systems Research, Technology Development, Validation and Roll Out – Second Edition

Work Package WP4

NA3 - Education and Training of Professionals, Researchers, and Students

Deliverable D4.4

D-NA3.3 Lessons Learned and Recommendations for Laboratory Education and E-learning Tools

Funding Instrument: Research and Innovation Action
Call: H2020-INFRAIA-2019-1
Call Topic: INFRAIA-01-2018-2019 Integrating Activities for Advanced Communities

Project Start: 1 April 2020
Project Duration: 61 months

Beneficiary in Charge: Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS)

Document Identifier: doi:[10.5281/zenodo.14746661](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14746661)

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	✓
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the Consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the Consortium (including the Commission Services)	

Deliverable Information

Document Administrative Information	
Project Acronym:	ERIGrid 2.0
Project Number:	870620
Deliverable Number:	D4.4
Deliverable Full Title:	D-NA3.3 Lessons Learned and Recommendations for Laboratory Education and E-learning Tools
Deliverable Short Title:	Lessons Learned and Recommendations
Document Identifier:	ERIGrid2-D44-LessonsLearnedAndRecommendations-submitted
Beneficiary in Charge:	Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS)
Report Version:	v1.7
Contractual Date:	31/01/2025
Report Submission Date:	07/03/2025
Dissemination Level:	PU
Nature:	Report
Lead Author(s):	A. Kontou, P. Kotsampopoulos (ICCS)
Co-author(s):	L. Ramos (DERlab), K. Heussen (DTU), E. Rikos (CRES), G. Silano (RSE), A. Acosta (RWTH), V. Subramaniam (TUD), Karafotis (HEDNO), T. Strasser (AIT), E. Widl (AIT)
Keywords:	Education, Training, E-learning tools, webinars, MOOC, Laboratory Education, Tutorials, Educational Strategy, Training Objectives, Intended Learning Outcomes, Feedback Analysis, European Union (EU), H2020, Project, ERIGrid 2.0, GA 870620
Status:	__ draft, __ final, <u>x</u> submitted

Change Log

Date	Version	Author/Editor	Summary of Changes Made
10/01/2025	v1.0	A. Kontou, P. Kotsampopoulos (ICCS)	Draft report structure created
31/01/2025	v1.1	A. Kontou, P. Kotsampopoulos (ICCS), L. Ramos (DERlab), K. Heussen (DTU), . . . , E. Widl (AIT)	Material inputs added
14/02/2025	v1.2	A. Kontou (ICCS)	Feedback and lessons learned added
21/02/2025	v1.3	A. Kontou (ICCS)	Final draft version for review
03/03/2025	v1.4	E. Mrakotsky (AIT)	Language and grammar check
04/03/2025	v1.5	I. Abdulhadi (UoS), M. Calin (AIT)	Internal review
06/03/2025	v1.6	A. Kontou (ICCS)	Reviewers' comments implemented
07/03/2025	v1.7	T. Strasser (AIT)	Final version

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	7
1. Introduction	8
1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document	8
1.2 Structure of the Document	8
2. Developed E-Learning Material and Lab Modules	9
2.1 Overview of the ERIGrid 2.0 E-Learning Material	9
2.2 Developments of the Second Period	12
2.3 ERIGrid 2.0 MOOC: “Holistic Smart Energy System Validation”	17
3. Feedback, Analysis, and Recommendations	22
3.1 Background and Feedback Collection Approach	22
3.2 Educators’ Feedback based on Activity Reporting	22
3.3 Learners’ Feedback	23
4. Lessons Learned and Recommendations	42
4.1 Practices for Innovative Teaching for Modern Energy Systems	42
4.2 ERIGrid 2.0 Training: Insights and Experiences	42
5. Conclusions	44
References	45
Appendix A: Activity Plans	46
A.1 Template for Activity Plan Form	46
A.2 Activity Plan Forms for Educational/Training Tools	49
A.3 Activity Plan Forms for Webinars	58
A.4 Activity Plan Forms for Virtual and Remote Labs	68
A.5 Activity Plan Forms for Other E-learning Material	79
A.6 Activity Plan Forms for Modules and Hands-on Lab Education	89
Appendix B: Activity Reports	95
B.1 Template for Activity Report Form	95

List of Figures

Figure 1: Snapshot of “A Step-By-Step Video Guide on ‘How to Build a Small Wind Turbine’” video available at the project’s YouTube channel.	13
Figure 2: Experimental setup for the evaluation of voltage/frequency protection.	14
Figure 3: Experimental results for the evaluation of the voltage/frequency protection tripping time. .	15
Figure 4: Overview of the designed microgrid and control layers.	16
Figure 5: Developed GUI for the execution of the lab module.	17
Figure 6: Structure of the ERIGrid 2.0 Massive Open Online Course.	18
Figure 7: Moodle environment of the ERIGrid 2.0 Massive Open Online Course.	18

List of Tables

Table 1: List of training and educational tools developed in ERIGrid 2.0 project.....	10
Table 2: List of webinars developed in ERIGrid 2.0 project and participation statistics.....	10
Table 3: List of virtual and remote laboratories developed in ERIGrid 2.0 project.	11
Table 4: List of other e-learning material developed in ERIGrid 2.0 project.	11
Table 5: List of laboratory modules developed in ERIGrid 2.0 project.	12

List of Abbreviations

AC	Alternating Current
API	Application Programming Interface
CHIL	Control Hardware-in-the-Loop
CPES	Cyber-Physical Energy System
DC	Direct Current
DG	Distributed Generator
DRTS	Distributed Real-Time Simulator
ERA-Net	European Research Area Network
GDRTS	Geographically Distributed Real-Time Simulation
GUI	Graphical User Interface
H2020	Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Framework Program
HIL	Hardware-in-the-Loop
HTD	Holistic Test Description
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
MOOC	Massive Open Online Course
MPPT	Maximum Power Point Tracking
NA	Networking Activities
NPS	Net Promoter Score
PA	Power Amplifier
PHIL	Power Hardware-in-the-Loop
PI	Proportional-Integral
PV	Photovoltaic
RES	Renewable Energy Source
RI	Research Infrastructure
RTS	Real Time Simulation
RTDS	Real Time Digital Simulator
SES	Smart Energy Systems
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics
WP	Work Package
WT	Wind Turbine

Executive Summary

The ERIGrid 2.0 training and educational developments and activities aim to inform, provide examples on the latest advancements, methodologies, tools for developing, validating, and deploying smart energy system solutions, and best practices to support the energy transition and the increased digitalisation of smart energy systems.

This deliverable starts with an overview of all the educational materials developed within ERIGrid 2.0. It includes summary tables detailing the resources developed during the first reporting period (M9-M36) and the second reporting period (M37-M58). Most of the e-learning tools and material were developed in the first phase to ensure their availability for later use and refinement. In the second reporting period, one tutorial video and two laboratory modules were created, which are thoroughly documented in this report. In total, the project resulted in the development of four (4) educational tools, six (6) webinars, four (4) virtual & remote laboratories, four (4) other e-learning materials and two (2) laboratory modules. A Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) consisting of 6 seminars was developed to provide training on Holistic Smart Energy Systems Validation, incorporating advancements in modern methodologies such as Hardware-in-the-Loop (HIL), co-simulation, Geographically Distributed Real-Time Simulation (GDRTS), holistic test case description methods, etc., achieved throughout the project.

The report further presents the feedback collection approach followed, analyses the survey results, and highlights key lessons learned and recommendations for future developments. Feedback was gathered from both educators and learners to gain insights into the content, target audience, learning objectives, achievements and statistics related to training activities and e-material. To facilitate this process, two reporting forms were developed and utilised: the Activity Plan Form, that collected information during the planning and preparation phase of the activities, and the Activity Report Form, that provided insights after the completion of each activity. To obtain feedback from the learners, customised surveys were distributed to users and participants. Looking back, it can be stated that higher-quality feedback and greater engagement was obtained from in-person activities compared to online surveys.

Finally, the report concludes with lessons learned and recommendations based on the overall training experience and the feedback received. Education and training are essential for equipping professionals with the necessary skills, requiring active, hands-on, and problem-based learning approaches. ERIGrid 2.0 aligned its educational strategy with (IEEE PES Task Force on Innovative Teaching Methods for Modern Power and Energy Systems, 2024) recommendations, identifying target learner groups and categorizing activities based on Bloom's taxonomy. Key insights from the educational activities highlighted the importance of hands-on training, user-friendly e-tools, structured learning formats, and tailored content for different skill levels. Additionally, the identified gender imbalance in participation underscores the need for targeted outreach to promote diversity in Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) education. Overall, the ERIGrid 2.0 training approach proved effective, demonstrating alignment with best practices for modern power and energy system education.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

To address the challenges arising from the rapid transformation of the power and energy sector, education must leverage modern, interactive learning methods and e-learning resources. Moreover, creating open-source material promotes wider accessibility and inclusivity, acting as a way to further accelerate innovation. Additionally, hands-on laboratory experience—whether through software-based educational tools, hardware experimental setups, or advanced validation methods like HIL—is essential for equipping learners with practical skills and a deeper understanding of emerging technologies.

To ensure the effectiveness and relevance of newly developed educational material, continuous assessment through feedback from both educators and learners is essential for refining and improving teaching approaches and tools. Furthermore, complementary training events, such as training schools, workshops, or webinars, are playing a vital role in education, establishing a communication channel and providing opportunities for direct interaction between learners and educators, facilitating knowledge exchange, and gathering valuable feedback for continuous improvement.

In that context, this deliverable aims to summarise the experiences, challenges and lessons learned identified during the development, implementation and evaluation of e-learning materials and educational events developed within ERIGrid 2.0. It provides an analysis and assessment of the impact of the delivered educational material and activities based on feedback obtained from the educators and learners. This document also provides recommendations for future improvements based on experience gained from challenges and best practices encountered. These insights aim to enhance the effectiveness and accessibility of educational practices by promoting replicability, and offering guidance to refine methodologies and optimize outcomes.

In summary, this report first provides an overview of the e-learning material and lab modules developed within ERIGrid 2.0. It then outlines the methodology used for feedback collection and presents an analysis of the gathered responses. The report concludes with key lessons learned and recommendations. Additionally, questionnaires and reporting material used in the evaluation process are included in the Annex.

1.2 Structure of the Document

This document is organised as follows: Section 2 gives an overview of the developed e-learning material and laboratory modules, Section 3 presents the feedback collection approach followed and the analysis of survey results, and Section 4 presents the lessons learned and recommendations resulting from the feedback collection analysis. The conclusions are presented in Section 5. Finally, the forms used to collect feedback from educators on the activities presented in this report are provided in Appendix A and Appendix B.

2 Developed E-Learning Material and Lab Modules

In Deliverable D4.3 (*D-NA3.2 Education and Training Material for E-learning and Laboratory Education, 2023*) the types and categories of e-learning material developed in the frame of ERIGrid 2.0, along with their definitions, are presented. The list is provided below for the reader's convenience and easy reference:

- *Educational/Training Tools*: Software programs that are used by educators and students to facilitate the educational process. Usually, they are designed for carrying out various types of analyses (steady-state, dynamic, etc.).
- *Interactive Notebooks*: Human-readable documents that contain code-based parts (Python, MATLAB, etc.) enriched with text elements (paragraphs, equations, figures, links, etc.).
- *Webinars*: Engaging online events in which a speaker or a group of speakers deliver presentations to an audience, which interact with them through questions, polls or any other interactive means.
- *Virtual Labs*: Interactive digitally simulated activities similar to the ones that take place in actual physical laboratories.
- *Remote Labs*: Online access to the physical infrastructure of a remote laboratory.
- *Other E-Learning Material*: Videos, presentations, and any other e-learning material.

Open-source platforms such as Zenodo¹, GitHub², YouTube³ and Moodle⁴ are used to host the developed resources, ensuring free and open access for all interested learners.

2.1 Overview of the ERIGrid 2.0 E-Learning Material

In this subsection, the complete lists of the e-learning content developed throughout the ERIGrid 2.0 project are presented.

2.1.1 Educational/Training Tools

Table 1 provides a list of the educational and training tools delivered as part of the ERIGrid 2.0 project. All the tools were developed during the 1st period (M9-M36), as expected.

2.1.2 Webinars

Table 2 provides a list of the webinars delivered as part of the ERIGrid 2.0 project. All webinars were developed during the 1st period (M9-M36), as expected. In addition, updated information on the webinar's participation statistics is presented. More details, about the webinars can be found in Appendix A.3.

¹<http://zenodo.org/communities/erigrd2/>

²<http://github.com/ERIGrid2/>

³<https://www.youtube.com/@ERIGrid-ResearchInfrastructure/>

⁴<https://erigrd2.eu/training/>

Table 1: List of training and educational tools developed in ERIGrid 2.0 project.

Software Tool	Description	Developer	Materials
<i>Open Source Load Flow Tool in Python</i> ^a	A load flow calculator was developed in Python that can be used either as an independent tool or as part of a composite tool calculator or control algorithm.	CRES	Materials , Appendix A.2.1
<i>Power Flow Jupyter Notebooks</i> ^a	Two Jupyter interactive notebooks were developed for power flow calculation in transmission networks, using Matlab and Python programming languages	ICCS	Materials , Appendix A.2.2
<i>Energy Analysis Tool for Microgrids and Islanded System</i> ^a	An open license that enables the user to conduct techno-economic studies on microgrids and island power systems.	CRES	Materials , Appendix A.2.3
<i>Smart Grid Applications Leveraging Machine Learning Principles</i> ^a	An open license tool developed in R that demonstrates the use of data-driven machine learning principles for the implementation of solar-specific smart grid applications.	UCY	Materials , Appendix A.2.4

^aActivity reported in (*D-NA3.2 Education and Training Material for E-learning and Laboratory Education*, 2023).

Table 2: List of webinars developed in ERIGrid 2.0 project and participation statistics.

Webinar Name	Registrants	Attendees	External Persons	Zenodo (15.02.2025)		Youtube Views (15.02.2025)
				Views	Downloads	
<i>Remote Testing & EIRIE Platform</i> ^a	169	93	79	690	798	243
<i>Recent Research Trends in Engineering and Validating Cyber-Physical Energy Systems</i> ^a	63	30	n/a	295	208	n/a
<i>Mosaik 3.0 – Open-Source Smart Grid Co-simulation Framework</i> ^a	46	46	32	804	677	1554
<i>Addressing the Growing Complexity of Power and Energy Systems through Interconnection of Geographically Distributed Research Laboratories</i> ^a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	103
<i>First Webinar of RICH Europe on Transnational and Virtual access opportunities (TA/VA)</i> ^a	n/a	65	n/a	137	68	n/a
<i>Design of Smart Grid Test Lab Infrastructure</i> ^a	n/a	30	25	n/a	n/a	n/a

2.1.3 Virtual and Remote Labs

Table 3 provides a list of the virtual and remote laboratories delivered as part of the ERIGrid 2.0 project. All services were developed during the 1st period (M9-M36), as expected.

Table 3: List of virtual and remote laboratories developed in ERIGrid 2.0 project.

Laboratory	Type of Lab	Description	Accessed Lab	Material
Solar-plus-storage system environmental and performance measurements ^a	Virtual lab	A virtual platform that allows users to access real-time environmental and operational data from the smart PV and battery storage inverters of a test-bench solar-plus-storage system installed at the UCY nanogrid.	UCY	Appendix A.4.1
UCY micro-grid real-time measurements ^a	Virtual lab	A virtual platform that allows users to access real-time environmental and operational data from the UCY's microgrid.	UCY	Appendix A.4.2
Environmental measurements and PV models ^a	Virtual lab	A virtual platform that allows access to environmental and operation data from actual PV systems.	CRES	Appendix A.4.3
Microgrid balancing experiment ^a	Remote lab	A simplified experiment that allows users to remotely connect to the experimental microgrid via a web-link and conduct balancing tests.	CRES	Appendix A.4.4

2.1.4 Other E-Learning Material

Table 4 provides a list of additional e-material not included in the above categories, delivered as part of the ERIGrid 2.0 project. The majority of the material was developed during the 1st period (M9-M36), as expected. The video about the construction of small Wind Turbine (WT) delivered the 2nd period (M37-M61).

Table 4: List of other e-learning material developed in ERIGrid 2.0 project.

Title	Type	Description	Developer	Materials
About ERIGrid 2.0 – Connecting European Smart Grid Research Infrastructures ^a	video	Introduction of the ERIGrid 2.0 vision, objectives, and related activities (incl. access activities).	AIT	Materials , Appendix A.5.1
Virtual Tour through the SysTec Lab ^a	virtual lab tour	Brief overview of different testing facilities at the test center SysTec located at Fraunhofer IEE, Kassel / Germany.	IEE	Appendix A.5.2
Advanced real-time supervision and centralised control of distributed energy resources in smart grids ^a	lecture/presentation	The advanced real-time supervision and centralised control of distributed energy resources in smart grids is a tutorial relevant to the topics of grid modernisation for high renewable shares and optimal operational management of DER in smart grids.	UCY	Materials Appendix A.5.3
Construction of small WT	video	Presents the whole process of manufacturing locally a small WT for rural electrification purposes.	ICCS	Appendix A.5.4

2.1.5 Modules and Hands-on Lab Education

Table 5 provides a list of the laboratory modules delivered as part of the ERIGrid 2.0 project. The modules were developed during the 2nd period (M37-M61).

Table 5: List of laboratory modules developed in ERIGrid 2.0 project.

Laboratory Module	Description	Developer	Materials
Conformance test procedures for PV inverters	Test procedures for assessing PV inverters basic characteristics including efficiency, MPPT accuracy, harmonics injection, anti-islanding response, DC current injection and leakage current protection.	CRES	Appendix A.6.1
Primary and secondary control techniques in inverter dominated microgrids using real-time digital simulation	Fundamental concepts of hierarchical control of inverter-based microgrids and insights regarding real-time digital simulation. Specifically, primary and secondary control techniques/algorithms are instructed using real-time simulation platform.	ICCS	Appendix A.6.2

2.2 Developments of the Second Period

This section details the e-learning material and laboratory modules developed during the 2nd period (M37-M61) of ERIGrid 2.0. Specifically, a comprehensive video was created demonstrating the whole process of manufacturing a small WT locally. Additionally, two laboratory modules were developed. The first focuses on conformance testing procedures for Photovoltaic (PV) inverters, while the second explores the hierarchical control of inverter dominated microgrids offering guided exercises on implementing primary and secondary control strategies. For the lab modules, hardware setups and real-time simulation systems were utilised.

2.2.1 Video: Construction of Small WT

About one billion people today do not have access to grid electricity, and small-scale renewable energy systems can empower rural communities to generate electricity from locally available resources, offering opportunities for improved and sustainable livelihoods. Locally manufactured small wind turbines contribute to this direction, often complementing other renewable energy technologies in small-scale hybrid systems. In addition, locally manufactured small wind turbines, as parts of renewable energy systems, offer electrification and decarbonisation services, as required for a net-zero future while meeting the relevant Sustainable Development Goals of the UN. While research is conducted in these fields at the ICCS, thus supporting various aspects of these ambitions, it is also necessary to develop educational tools to facilitate the empowerment of citizens in the renewable energy transition. This educational video on how to manufacture locally a small wind turbine, aims at developing such perspectives.

A video (cf. Figure 1) that describes the manufacturing process of a 2.4 m rotor diameter small wind turbine has been filmed and edited by the ICCS. The video describes in detail the manufacturing of the wooden blades and hub, of the generator stator and coils, of the generator rotor and magnets, of the metal support frame, and of the tail boom and vane. The audience of the video comprises members of the Wind Empowerment network, and all local manufacturers of residential small wind turbines. Wind Empowerment consists of more than 50 member organisations on all continents, such as cooperatives, collectives, enterprises, non-governmental organisations, research groups, universities, institutions, training centres, as well

as hundreds of individual practitioners around the world. This video supports the development of locally manufactured small wind turbines, thus accelerating the validation and deployment of novel technologies, which is part of the ERIGrid 2.0 agenda.

A Step-By-Step Video Guide on “How to Build a Small Wind Turbine”

Figure 1: Snapshot of “A Step-By-Step Video Guide on ‘How to Build a Small Wind Turbine’” video available at the project’s YouTube channel.

So far the video has attracted a lot of interest with 19,224 views and 226 likes on YouTube.

2.2.2 Lab Module: Conformance Test Procedures for Photovoltaic Inverters

This module considers actions and equipment required for testing PV inverters concerning their conformance with international standards. Today, PV inverters are a predominant technology due to the rapid growth of Renewable Energy Source (RES) and especially PVs at different voltage levels. This growth occurs mainly at the distribution level but can also affect transmission systems, especially when the penetration level of RES becomes high. One reason for this is the particular operational behaviour of these inverters compared to other conventional devices (i.e., loads) connected to the grid. Several important aspects have to be taken into account during the design and integration of a PV inverter, including harmonics injection, anti-islanding protection, efficiency, etc. Such issues are usually tackled with the use of specific standardised procedures. Exemplary related standards are IEEE 1547⁵ and IEC 62116⁶.

In this context, the specific module provides an overview of the most commonly used tests related to the PV inverters’ conformance with the grid regulations. The presentation of these procedures is a simplified version in line with the relevant standards and aims to provide a guideline to engineers and researchers on how to characterize a prototype inverter. In addition,

⁵<https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/1547/5915/>

⁶<https://webstore.iec.ch/en/publication/6479/>

the second objective is to familiarize the user with the interconnection requirements and testing procedures usually required in such applications.

Upon examining related standards and procedures to develop the specific module, concrete test categories can be distinguished as follows:

- Performance tests,
- Interference tests, and
- Protection tests.

The above-mentioned categories include an assortment of tests, which provide more insights regarding these areas of interest. The tests described in this module are the following:

- Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) accuracy,
- Efficiency measurement,
- Harmonics injection,
- Direct Current (DC) current injection,
- PV leakage current, and
- Anti-islanding protection (i.e., voltage/frequency protection).

As can be seen in Figure 2 the setup for testing the voltage/frequency protection involves the use of a Grid Simulator for reproducing the relevant Alternating Current (AC) conditions (i.e., stepwise changes in voltage and frequency), a PV simulator as the inverter input, and an oscilloscope used to record the response time of the protection. As an alternative to using a PV emulator, a controllable DC/DC converter or an actual PV array can be used. Indicative results for the specific test are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 2: Experimental setup for the evaluation of voltage/frequency protection.

Figure 3: Experimental results for the evaluation of the voltage/frequency protection tripping time.

2.2.3 Lab Module: Primary and Secondary Control Techniques in Microgrids

This lab module educates students on the hierarchical control of inverter dominated microgrids, focusing on primary and secondary control techniques. It also offers hands-on experience with the real-time simulation platform of Real Time Digital Simulator (RTDS) Technologies. The adoption of Distributed Generator (DG) technologies, including microturbines, PVs, fuel cells, and small WT, is steadily increasing as a viable option to meet growing energy demands, reduce energy costs, and advance sustainability goals. These technologies are being integrated into low- or medium-voltage distribution networks, traditionally viewed as energy consumers. The integration of the generation transforms them from passive consumers into dynamic producers capable of bidirectional power flow.

To effectively integrate microgeneration and variable consumption loads, a local control system that efficiently coordinates and manages the assets is essential. This concept underscores the importance of microgrids as highly controllable and flexible systems that can operate both in interconnected mode with other systems or independently in island mode. Their modularity and flexibility have the potential to enhance the robustness, resilience, and efficiency of smart energy systems, positioning microgrids as key enablers of the energy transition. Moreover, integrating advanced laboratory testing methods, such as real-time simulation and HIL techniques, into education offers hands-on learning experiences. These are equipping young generations with applied knowledge, a deeper understanding of component and system level operation, and essential validation procedures relevant to both academic and industrial environments.

In this context, the specific module aims to familiarise students and young engineers with fun-

fundamental concepts of inverter dominated microgrids, and to enhance the understanding of the following primary and secondary control techniques/algorithms:

- Conventional Droop Control,
- Generalized Droop Control,
- Centralized Secondary Control, and
- Distributed Level Averaging Proportional-Integral (PI) Secondary Control.

Additionally, the module aims to provide hands-on experience with real-time simulation using the RTDS simulator and foster intuitive understanding of design trade-offs, a critical aspect of an engineer’s daily work.

Figure 4 presents the overview of the microgrid designed in the RTDS, along with its hierarchical control layers. The topology is highly configurable, and a user-friendly Graphical User Interface (GUI) has been developed to facilitate transitions between the different control modes, enhancing user experience, as presented in Figure 5.

Figure 4: Overview of the designed microgrid and control layers.

Figure 6: Structure of the ERIGrid 2.0 Massive Open Online Course.

Figure 7: Moodle environment of the ERIGrid 2.0 Massive Open Online Course.

2.3.1 Seminar 1: “Introduction to the ERIGrid 2.0 MOOC”

This module serves as an introduction to the MOOC and consists of four parts. It begins by outlining the scope of the ERIGrid 2.0 RI project focusing on the trends and future directions of the development of the smart energy systems, the importance of integrated RIs for offering advanced services and the challenges related to the planning and operation of the energy infrastructures. The energy sector is undergoing deep transformation driven by its critical importance in achieving sustainability and particularly its fundamental role in addressing climate change. Digitalisation serves as a key enabler to the energy system’s transition, but it also demands personnel with adequate skills to adapt and excel in this new era.

To address this need, the skill gaps identified by the Erasmus+ EDDIE⁷ project, which must be bridged to meet industry targets, are presented. E-learning material plays a crucial role in equipping learners with tools to enhance their practical knowledge and address the skill gaps. To this end, ERIGrid 2.0 has developed a range of e-learning resources and virtual services designed to strengthen the hands-on skills of young engineers. This module concludes with an overview of these resources grouped into thematic categories aligned with the scope of ERIGrid 2.0 and it presents selected examples.

⁷<https://eddie-erasmus.eu/>

2.3.2 Seminar 2: “Multi-Energy Networks”

This module consists of three main parts. First, the motivation and background for simulation and in particular co-simulation in the context of the challenges of modern energy systems are given. Due to the increasing complexity of the system, different domains and timescales have to be considered and simulation has to integrate different models to allow detailed investigation. The second part introduces the co-simulation framework Mosaik⁸ and is subdivided into two videos.

The first gives an overview and describes the architecture and Application Programming Interface (API) of Mosaik, while the second shows a tutorial for a simple Mosaik simulation. This tutorial demonstrates how models can be coupled with Mosaik and a simple co-simulation scenario can be executed. The third part of this module shows the multi-energy benchmark as an example of a more complex simulation scenario to investigate the inter-domain effects of coupled multi-domain distribution networks. It contains two differently implemented co-simulation scenarios of an electricity and a heat grid, which are connected by a heat pump. The scenario is accessible at Zenodo (*ERIGrid2/benchmark-model-multi-energy-networks: v1.0*, 2021) and GitHub⁹.

2.3.3 Seminar 3: “Hardware-in-the-loop Validation for Modern Energy Systems”

The requirements for testing of power system components have been substantially increased in the previous years with the realization of the smart grid scenario. Control and power devices serving multiple purposes and adhering to various and complex grid codes are needed today in our power systems. However, the testing of such devices remains a challenging task, as direct field application may cause high costs and risks. Hence, laboratory validation is widely applied for smart grid components. This module consists of three parts and aims to introduce learners to Real Time Simulation (RTS) and HIL techniques.

The first part explains the importance of HIL validation methods and presents experiences with Control Hardware-in-the-Loop (CHIL) for testing advanced protection schemes, inverter controllers and industrial power plant controllers. The second part focuses on Power Hardware-in-the-Loop (PHIL), in which a Distributed Real-Time Simulator (DRTS) simulates the power system under consideration and the hardware device under test is interfaced with the simulated system through a power amplifier. However, the relatively complicated setup consisting of the DRTS, the Power Amplifier (PA), the sensors and the interfacing cards, leads to accuracy and stability concerns for the PHIL testing procedure. This module aims to fill the educational gap in the above stated problem. Maximizing the utilization of available RI capabilities and expanding the range of provided services is another crucial aspect that draws a lot of attention. To this end, the third part of this module introduces learners to GDRTS, a technique that enables the integration and coordination of remote laboratories with diverse equipment and computational resources.

Insights are provided into the implementation of GDRTS setups, challenges related to the stability and accuracy are explained and experimental examples are presented to illustrate its practical applications.

⁸<https://mosaik.offis.de/>

⁹<https://github.com/ERIGrid2/benchmark-model-multi-energy-networks/>

2.3.4 Seminar 4: “Multi-Lab Experiments”

The increasing complexity of today’s energy systems, which incorporate multiple energy sources, necessitates a distributed methodology for conducting experiments. This is because a single RI can rarely provide the required resources to study such a complex system comprehensively. The ability to study these systems is often constrained by several factors, including the lack of multi-domain laboratories, detailed large-scale models, confidentiality concerns, and limited expertise. Hence, this module consists of 3 parts and aims to address these challenges by covering the motivation, techniques/tools, and real-life demonstrations of GDRTS experiments. These experiments are designed to overcome some of the aforementioned limitations. The module includes discussions on techniques for simulations, and co-simulations using cloud and edge solutions, all while ensuring cyber security.

2.3.5 Seminar 5: “Design and Documentation of Complex Test System Setups”

Smart energy systems solutions often involve several interactions between components, interfacing energy forms, and several engineering domains. For example, a smart voltage controller needs to be tested conjointly with the distribution grid and may rely on communications infrastructure. The characterization and validation of such solutions through testing, as well as the reproducibility of test results, require a clear scoping of test conditions and purposes. The ERI-Grid Holistic Test Description (HTD) offers a means to facilitate this scoping and documentation of test plans.

This module introduces this methodology in three parts. It will motivate where and why systematic test description is helpful, and introduce the basic concepts applied in test description. Via several examples, the basic concepts and their practical application are illustrated, covering the full range of HTD documentation from test case to experiment specification (example journey). The learning module is supported by learning tools such as a self-test quiz. The final part of the module contextualizes the HTD approach with related smart grid standards and interoperability testing approaches.

2.3.6 Seminar 6: “Industry’s Opinion”

Finally, this part aims to inform the industry community about the project’s activities, is presented. This module includes three parts. In the first part, a brief introduction of ERIGrid 2.0 is presented. ERIGrid 2.0 focuses on enhancing smart grid development by integrating industry perspectives and promoting a cyber-physical systems-based approach. The project aims to bridge the gap between academic research and industrial application by offering access to advanced testing facilities, research services, and simulation tools.

The second part includes an Industry Engagement Survey, conducted within the scope of the ERIGrid 2.0 project. Several key important findings were derived from the survey. First, concerning industry testing needs, strong demand was observed for validation of substation automation systems, standardization of grid-user equipment, and cross-domain component interaction testing to improve interoperability. Key barriers include technical complexity, lack of awareness, and uncertainty about the commercial viability of such approaches.

The third part presents the Industrial Lab Access Success Stories. ERIGrid 2.0 supported 23 user proposals involving industrial partners, 16 led by industrial organizations. These projects

provided 209 access days across various research infrastructures, with additional projects expected to extend this number further. In conclusion, ERIGrid 2.0 serves as a key enabler for industry-driven research and innovation in smart grids. By providing access to cutting-edge laboratories, co-simulation environments, and real-time data platforms, the initiative empowers stakeholders to develop, test, and standardize next-generation energy solutions.

3 Feedback, Analysis, and Recommendations

3.1 Background and Feedback Collection Approach

This section presents, compiles and analyses feedback obtained on various educational activities and e-learning material developed within the frame of ERIGrid 2.0. A methodological approach was followed to gather input from both educators and learners, including event participants, students and users of tools. To assess the effectiveness of educational and training events and material delivered in ERIGrid 2.0, two forms were developed and distributed to partners. On one hand, the “Activity Plan” form was utilised to collect insights from the educators on target groups, intended training objectives and learning outcomes, and the overall scope of the activities concerning ERIGrid 2.0 targets and objectives.

Based on these forms, an analysis was conducted, with the results presented in Deliverables D4.1 (*D-NA3.1a Report on the Training Workshops and Staff Exchanges, 2023*) and D4.2 (*D-NA3.1b Report on the Training Workshops and Staff Exchanges, 2025*), within the section outlining the educational strategy developed for managing the educational content created as part of the ERIGrid 2.0 project. On the other hand, the “Activity Report” form was distributed to the developers of educational content to gather information on the actual implementation of activities/material. For feedback collection from the learners, customised questionnaires were also distributed during some activities and e-learning material, as detailed in later sections. Following the analysis on the feedback, Section 4 presents lessons learned, best practices and recommendations for smart grid education, integrating insights gained from the feedback collected throughout the project.

3.2 Educators’ Feedback based on Activity Reporting

ERIGrid 2.0 included, as part of the activities, the organisation of training and educational activities such as workshops, seminars, training schools, etc. Each activity was accompanied by a planning process established at the beginning of the project. In the first step of this process, the activity is described in detail through the “Activity Plan” in which the overview of the activity, a short description of the topic covered, intended audience, motivation, as well as its outline, objectives, and expected outcomes are described. Once the activity details were defined, the activity was disseminated via social channels and networks until it took place. During most relevant activities, feedback from participants is usually collected through questionnaires at the end of the session. Such feedback allowed the improvement of further activities and the collection of lessons learned. Lastly, the “Activity Report” was developed to recap the topics presented, attendance of the activity, feedback obtained (where applicable). Activity Report Forms were mainly used for physical events and activities to collect information post-delivery, including details on participation, achievements, and other relevant outcomes. Any relevant material was further uploaded in open-access repositories, websites, etc.

As part of the activities of Work Package (WP)4 “*Networking Activities (NA)3 - Education and Training of Professionals, Researchers, and Students*” an analysis on the ERIGrid 2.0 training and educational activities was performed in Month 36 (approximately in the middle of the project duration) and at the end of the project. This study aimed to analyse the following aspects:

- Trending topics areas covered by the training activities from a pre-established list of topics within the scope of ERIGrid 2.0.
- Validation methods implemented during the activity (if any).

- Target groups addressed for the activities.
- Level of cognitive skills reached by the participants according to the learning objectives of the training activities (Bloom's taxonomy) ("Bloom's taxonomy: Original and revised", 2005).
- Activity format and other relevant classifiers.

These studies analysed the activity plans and reports of each educational and training activity to quantify each of the aforementioned aspects. The mid-term study gave insights on those topic areas, audience not covered or relegated until that moment in the project. By doing this, it was possible to take corrective actions in favour of the project ambitions. Therefore, the educators had the opportunity to adjust some aspects of further activities accordingly. The final report validated the effectiveness of such adjustments, which allowed, among other things, covering all topics and target groups as well as concluding the preferred formats, validation methods, etc. Moreover, feedback obtained during the relevant activities allowed educators to refine educational methodologies and other aspects described in subsequent sections.

3.3 Learners' Feedback

As previously mentioned, to evaluate the impact of the training and educational activities and gather feedback on the ERIGrid 2.0 educational material and events, questionnaires were developed and distributed to learners (tool users, event participants, etc.). Such feedback was collected for selected activities considered most impactful, ensuring the capture of meaningful insights that can inform improvements. This subsection presents the survey¹⁰ results for these activities. Firstly, feedback on the use of the educational tools is provided, followed by participants' feedback on the ERIGrid 2.0 training schools and workshops.

3.3.1 Feedback on E-Learning Tools

This section presents the feedback obtained for the e-learning tools developed within the project. A questionnaire was designed to collect insights on the use of the educational tools. It aimed to assess users' backgrounds, overall satisfaction, and the cognitive level achieved through their experience with the tools. Finally, the survey results from the laboratory session conducted at NTUA using Jupyter Notebooks are presented.

Survey on E-Learning Tools

The ERIGrid 2.0 Online Survey on Educational Tools aimed to assess the usability, effectiveness, and impact of the ERIGrid 2.0 educational tools used for smart grid learning. The survey specifically focused on the assessment of the tools:

- Power Flow Jupyter Notebooks,
- Load Flow Tool in Python,
- Flexxy, and
- Smart grid applications using machine learning in R Studio.

¹⁰<https://forms.office.com/r/MBBKC9EtTP>

The survey was designed to collect responses from a diverse group of participants, including students, researchers, educators, and industry professionals. However, because access to tools was provided freely, only a total of 6 users participated in the survey and provided their responses. It focused on evaluating key aspects such as:

- Overall user satisfaction with the tools,
- Ease of use and user-friendliness,
- Alignment with learning objectives,
- Impact on knowledge retention and application,
- Technical issues and bugs, and
- Willingness to recommend the tool to others.

The key findings of the survey can be summarised in the following points:

- The overall experience was rated from “Very Dissatisfied” to “Very Satisfied,” reflecting diverse user experiences.
- Ease of use was another critical factor, with some tools being perceived as more intuitive than others.
- Some tools were highly aligned with users’ learning objectives, while others were seen as less relevant.
- The majority of the users reported that the tools improved their ability to comprehend, analyse, and synthesize information.
- Some users reported encountering bugs or difficulties that impacted their learning experience.
- Despite some issues and the partial dissatisfaction with the use of the tools, all users agreed that they would/maybe recommend the tools to others.

The survey and the responses are presented below.

1. Age

● Under 18	0
● 18-24	1
● 25-34	4
● 35-44	0
● 45-54	0
● 55-64	1
● 65 or above	0
● Prefer not to say	0

2. Gender

● Female	2
● Male	4
● Other	0

3. Role

● Undergraduate/ PhD Student	3
● Young Professional	0
● Researcher	2
● Educator/Teacher	0
● Industry Worker	1
● Other	0

4. Please choose the tool that you used

● Power Flow Jupyter Notebooks	4
● Load Flow Tool in Python	1
● Flexxy	1
● Smart grid applications leveraging machine learning principles in R Studio	0

5. How would you rate the overall experience with the educational tool?

● Very Dissatisfied	1
● Dissatisfied	1
● Neutral	1
● Satisfied	2
● Very Satisfied	1

6. How user-friendly do you find the interface of the tool?

● Very Dissatisfied	1
● Dissatisfied	0
● Neutral	1
● Satisfied	4
● Very Satisfied	0

7. How would you rate the tool's alignment with your learning goals and objectives?

● Misaligned	2
● Neutral	0
● Somewhat aligned	1
● Moderately aligned	1
● Highly aligned	2

8. How has the educational tool impacted your ability to retain and apply knowledge?

● I could remember and recall key concepts more easily with the help of the tool.	0
● The tool facilitated a better grasp of concepts, enabling me to comprehend the...	2
● I could apply the acquired knowledge in some scenarios.	1
● The tool helped me analyze information to a certain extent.	0
● The tool supported me in evaluating information.	2
● The tool enhanced my ability to synthesize information and create meaningful...	1

9. Would you recommend this education tool to others?

● Yes	5
● No	0
● Maybe	1

Survey on the Jupyter Notebooks Laboratory Session

The Jupyter Notebooks were used at NTUA for laboratory education on power systems. The survey aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of Jupyter Notebooks as an educational tool, particularly in laboratory exercises related to power systems. A total of 21 participants provided

feedback, evaluating various aspects such as usefulness, user-friendliness, learning impact, and teaching support.

A total of 21 survey responses were collected, and the statistical analysis is presented below. The key findings of the survey can be summarised in the following points:

- 17 out of 21 participants (81%) found Jupyter Notebooks to be a useful educational tool.
- 18 participants (86%) agreed that Jupyter Notebooks helped them understand the problem-solving stages of load flow analysis better than just recording final results.
- 18 out of 21 participants (86%) found Jupyter Notebooks user-friendly and easy to use.
- 16 participants (76%) agreed that they could understand the power system concepts explored in the exercises despite the complexity of the code. However, 5 participants found the complexity to be a barrier to understanding.
- 17 participants (81%) felt that student participation and contributions were encouraged.
- 17 participants (81%) were satisfied with the teaching staff’s support and the presentation of topics.
- 19 participants (90%) agreed that the laboratory exercises improved their understanding of power systems.

The survey and the responses are presented below.

1. *The topics covered in the laboratory exercise are insightful.*

● Very much	5
● Quite a lot	9
● Moderately	5
● A little	1
● Not at all	1

2. *Jupyter Notebooks are a useful educational tool.*

● Very much	6
● Quite a lot	11
● Moderately	3
● A little	1
● Not at all	0

3. With Jupyter Notebooks I gained a deeper understanding of load flow problems.

● Very much	8
● Quite a lot	10
● Moderately	2
● A little	0
● Not at all	1

4. Jupyter Notebooks is a user-friendly and easy-to-use tool.

● Very much	7
● Quite a lot	9
● Moderately	3
● A little	2
● Not at all	0

5. I was able to understand the power system phenomena explored in the exercise.

● Very much	8
● Quite a lot	6
● Moderately	5
● A little	2
● Not at all	0

6. Active student participation and contributions are encouraged.

● Very much	11
● Quite a lot	6
● Moderately	3
● A little	0
● Not at all	1

7. The presentation of topics and support provided by the teaching staff were satisfactory.

● Very much	14
● Quite a lot	5
● Moderately	1
● A little	0
● Not at all	1

8. The laboratory exercise helped me to understand the operation of power systems.

● Very much	5
● Quite a lot	8
● Moderately	6
● A little	2
● Not at all	0

3.3.2 Feedback on Training/Educational Events and Activities

Deliverable D4.1 (*D-NA3.1a Report on the Training Workshops and Staff Exchanges, 2023*), provides an overview of the various educational activities and events organised within the framework of the ERIGrid 2.0 project. This subsection presents the feedback gathered from the ERIGrid 2.0 training schools and workshops, offering valuable insights into their effectiveness and impact. To gather participant perspectives, customised questionnaires were distributed to attendees of the events, capturing their experiences, overall satisfaction with the events and further suggestions for improvement.

Feedback: Training School on Digitalisation of Smart Energy Systems

ERIGrid 2.0, in collaboration with the Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Framework Program (H2020) SINERGY¹¹ project related to smart and innovate energy management and Smart Energy Systems (SES) European Research Area Network (ERA-Net) RESili8¹² project related to resilience in Cyber-Physical Energy System (CPES), organised a successful online training series on the digitalisation of smart energy systems from February 19-22, 2024. The total number of participants was 120 people. For more information on the training school refer to (*D-NA3.1b Report on the Training Workshops and Staff Exchanges, 2025*).

A survey was distributed to the participants aimed to evaluate the experience of the participants of the school. A total of 14 participants provided feedback from which the following key findings were extracted:

- The attendees comprised a diverse group of researchers, engineers, students, and teachers, with researchers making up the largest portion at 43%.

¹¹<https://project-sinergy.org/>

¹²<https://www.resili8-project.eu/>

- The lectures that attracted more interest were “Modelling and Simulation of Integrated Energy Systems” and “Cyber-Physical Tests Beds for Validation of Large-Scale Smart Grid Apps”.
- All lectures received ratings in four key aspects: Relevance of content, clarity of presentation, engagement of speaker. The responses were highly positive, with the majority of ratings falling between “Good” and “Excellent”.
- The majority of the respondents were satisfied with the covered topic areas. Some respondents wanted more coverage of cybersecurity issues and challenges of energy storage.
- A slightly negative Net Promoter Score (NPS) suggests room for improvement in the application of the knowledge gained from the lectures, as there were more detractors than promoters.
- The vast majority of the 12 respondents (86%) expressed interest in similar training, while no one responded negatively.
- Most attendees (69%) found the training through online sources, social media, and promotional activities. However, a notable portion of attendees also found out about the event through word of mouth.

Thus, both the survey and the responses are presented below.

1. Which age group do you belong to?

● Under 18	0
● 18-24	1
● 25-34	10
● 35-44	2
● 45-54	0
● 55-64	0
● 65 or above	0
● Prefer not to say	1

2. Gender

● Woman	6
● Man	8
● Non-binary	0
● Prefer not to say	0

3. Role

● Student	3
● Young Professional	0
● Researcher	6
● Engineer	3
● Teacher	1
● Other	1

4. Which lectures did you attend?

● Modelling and simulation of int...	12
● Integrated Energy Services, Cyb...	11
● Designing and Validating Cyber-...	7
● Cyber-Physical Tests Beds for Va...	7

5. Please rate the following aspects of "Lecture 1: Modelling and simulation of integrated energy systems".

■ Poor
 ■ Fair
 ■ Good
 ■ Very Good
 ■ Excellent

6. Please rate the following aspects of “Lecture 2: Integrated Energy Services, Cyber Security Issues, and Analytical Services”.

■ Poor
 ■ Fair
 ■ Good
 ■ Very Good
 ■ Excellent

7. Please rate the following aspects of “Lecture 3: Designing and Validating Cyber-Physical Energy Systems”.

■ Poor
 ■ Fair
 ■ Good
 ■ Very Good
 ■ Excellent

8. Please rate the following aspects of “Lecture 4: Cyber-Physical Tests Beds for Validation of Large-Scale Smart Grid Apps”.

■ Poor
 ■ Fair
 ■ Good
 ■ Very Good
 ■ Excellent

9. Which lecture did you find most beneficial and why?

- “All 4 Lecturer is Good for us but Cyber-Physical Tests Beds for Validation of Large-Scale Smart Grid Apps is very beneficial for me.”
- “Cyber-Physical Tests Beds for Validation of Large-Scale Smart Grid Apps.”
- “Lecture 4: I am doing my research and teaching in that area.”
- “The day 4 lecture was interesting to me, because the demo part was helping to visualise the things. Though, it was different area of my research work. I am working in the area of cyber security in smart grid with respect to applications like wide area monitoring.”
- “Lecture 2. In my field and I was related with the topic.”
- “Lecture 1: Modelling and simulation of integrated energy systems.”
- “The first, for the introduction to the use of cosimulation with mosaik.”

10. Were there any topics or areas you wished were covered during the training series but were not?

- “No”
- “No”
- “Challenges of energy storage in DER integration”
- “Almost all aspects were covered”
- “Particularly no”
- “Overall, it was satisfactory”
- “I was expecting cyber security issues to be covered in more details in the second lecture”

11. How likely are you to apply the knowledge gained from these lectures in your work or studies?

Promoters	3
Passives	7
Detractors	4

12. Overall, how satisfied are you with the online training series?

Promoters	3
Passives	8
Detractors	3

13. Do you have any additional comments or suggestions for improving future training events?

- “Please try to include other simulators also such as Typhoon and RTDS”
- “It’s good if we can have more training sessions”
- “No”

14. Would you be interested in similar training series in the future?

15. How did you hear about this training series?

Feedback: Summer School on Advanced Operation and Control of Active Distribution Networks: 2nd Edition

ERIGrid 2.0 project partners ICCS-NTUA and HEDNO organized the 2nd Summer School on “Advanced operation and control of active distribution networks”, in Athens, Greece, on 3-6 June 2024. The organisation of the event was supported by DERlab, TUD and UCY. The total number of participants was 24 people. For more information on the training school refer to (*D-NA3.1b Report on the Training Workshops and Staff Exchanges, 2025*).

A survey was distributed to the participants aimed to evaluate the experience of the participants of the training school. A total of 14 participants provided feedback on this activity. The key findings of the survey are summarised in the following points:

- The roles of the participants show a good balance between academic (undergraduate/PhD students, educator/teacher/professor) and professional backgrounds (young professionals, industry professionals, researchers), with a slight emphasis on academic involvement (57.2% total).

- Day 1 and Day 2 received the most positive feedback, with 100% of responses rated as “Good” or “Excellent”.
- The lab sessions received mostly favourable feedback, especially on Day 2 (64.3% “Very Satisfied”). This suggests that the hands-on component was a key strength of the event, with participants feeling they gained tangible skills and insights.
- The lab sessions seemed to have had a positive impact on knowledge retention. Many participants felt the sessions helped them grasp concepts better (42.9% for Day 1 and 21.4% for Day 2).
- The HEDNO facilities visit garnered high satisfaction (92.8% either “Very Satisfied” or “Somewhat Satisfied”). This suggests that on-site visits are a valuable aspect of the program, providing real-world exposure to complement theoretical knowledge.
- Similarly, the visit to Meltemi pilot site satisfied 75% of the participants.
- Vast majority of the respondents found the program aligned with their learning goals (93% “Highly aligned” or “Somewhat aligned”). This is a positive indicator that the content was relevant.
- The program’s organization was rated highly (100% “Very Satisfied” or “Satisfied”, 78.6% “Very Satisfied”).
- The likelihood to recommend the event was very high (100% “Very Likely” or “Likely”, 78.6% “Very Likely”), indicating strong satisfaction with the event and its value to participants.

The survey and the responses are presented below.

1. Which age group do you belong to?

2. Gender

● Female	2
● Male	11
● Other	0
● Prefer not to say	1

3. Role

● Undergraduate/ PhD Student	4
● Young Professional	4
● Researcher	3
● Educator/Teacher/Professor	2
● Industry Professional	1
● Other	0

4. How easy was the registration process?

● Very easy	12
● Easy	1
● Neutral	1
● Difficult	0

5. Did you attend the Day 1 of the summer school?

● Yes	14
● No	0

6. How would you rate the quality of the content provided in Day 1?

● Excellent	11
● Good	3
● Average	0
● Poor	0

7. How satisfied are you with the laboratory session of Day 1?

● Very satisfied	5
● Somewhat satisfied	8
● Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied	1
● Somewhat dissatisfied	0
● Very dissatisfied	0

8. How has the laboratory session of Day 1 impacted your ability to retain and apply knowledge?

● I could remember and recall key concepts more easily.	2
● Facilitated a better grasp of concepts, enabling me to comprehend the informatio...	6
● I could apply the acquired knowledge in some scenarios.	3
● Helped me analyze information to a certain extent.	2
● Supported me in evaluating information.	0
● Enhanced my ability to synthesize information and create meaningful connections betwee...	1

9. Any recommendations for improvements or any other comment for Day 1?

- “Maybe some exercises are best to do following and copying instructor example.”
- “Share the slides beforehand the lab session.”
- “Some points may have been lost just through the sheer volume of material. However, we have the material to go over again. Potentially could have done with more examples and exercises on the application of fundamental electrical engineering and control concepts.”

10. Did you attend the Day 2 of the summer school?

- Yes 14
- No 0

11. How would you rate the quality of the content provided in Day 2?

- Excellent 9
- Good 5
- Average 0
- Poor 0

12. How satisfied are you with the laboratory session of Day 2?

- Very satisfied 9
- Somewhat satisfied 4
- Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied 0
- Somewhat dissatisfied 1
- Very dissatisfied 0

13. How has the laboratory session of Day 2 impacted your ability to retain and apply knowledge?

- I could remember and recall key concepts more easily. 6
- Facilitated a better grasp of concepts, enabling me to comprehend the informatio... 3
- I could apply the acquired knowledge in some scenarios. 2
- Helped me analyze information to a certain extent. 0
- Supported me in evaluating information. 2
- Enhanced my ability to synthesize information and create meaningful connections between... 1

14. Any recommendations for improvements or any other comments for Day 2?

- *“Most points have been lost while a lot of space for improvement in the CHIL Workshop due to the weak connection of theoretical presentation and practical exercises. More effort must be given to explain the related fundamental concepts such as Droop and PI Control, the physical meaning of d-axis and q-axis, as well as d-q components, the related Equations and more discussion about the results, since the participants were multi-disciplinary engineers and researchers, while for many of them it was the first time to come in contact with the topic.”*

15. Did you attend the visit of HEDNO facilities?

- Yes 14
- No 0

16. How satisfied are you with the visit to HEDNO facilities?

- Very satisfied 8
- Somewhat satisfied 5
- Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied 1
- Somewhat dissatisfied 0
- Very dissatisfied 0

17. Did you attend the Day 4 of the summer school?

- Yes 12
- No 2

18. How would you rate the quality of the content provided in Day 4?

● Excellent	5
● Good	5
● Average	2
● Poor	0

19. How satisfied are you with the visit to Meltemi pilot site?

● Very satisfied	6
● Somewhat satisfied	3
● Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied	2
● Somewhat dissatisfied	1
● Very dissatisfied	0

20. Any recommendations for improvements or any other comments for Day 4?

- “Absolutely lovely trip”

21. How would you rate the summer school’s alignment with your learning goals and objectives?

● Highly aligned	7
● Somewhat aligned	6
● Neutral	1
● Somewhat misaligned	0
● Misaligned	0

22. How satisfied are you with the overall organisation of the summer school?

● Very satisfied	11
● Satisfied	3
● Neutral	0
● Dissatisfied	0
● Very dissatisfied	0

23. How likely are you to recommend this summer school to others?

● Very likely	11
● Likely	3
● Neutral	0
● Unlikely	0
● Very unlikely	0

24. Do you have any suggestions for improving the summer school?

- *“You are doing great, continue improving the same direction.”*
- *“Share the presentations/material beforehand.”*
- *“A brief overview of the fundamental electrical engineering concepts with more examples and laboratory exercises can help the multi-disciplinary participants to understand the material much better. Moreover, presentations from industry experts and other EU Universities will be beneficial for the summer school.”*

4 Lessons Learned and Recommendations

This section highlights and summarises the lessons learned and recommendations from the overall process of creating and managing educational content in ERIGrid 2.0, as well as the feedback analysis performed in Section 3. The lessons learned encompass both organisational and technical perspectives. Additionally, this section shares experiences and recommendations based on ERIGrid 2.0 members' active participation in dedicated educational panel sessions, task forces, and knowledge exchange with other projects.

4.1 Practices for Innovative Teaching for Modern Energy Systems

Modern energy systems are facing challenges such as the decentralisation of energy production, the increased integration of inverter-based resources that result in reduced system inertia, the interconnection of diverse energy carriers, evolving market models, and the widespread use of Information and Communications Technology (ICT)s across all sectors. Addressing these complexities requires new skills and multi-disciplinary expertise across various domains. Education and training play a crucial role in the preparation of the next generation of professionals and innovators to address current and future challenges. Nevertheless, the educational and training methods must be adapted to meet the new needs, ensuring effective, active, problem-based, and hands-on learning. Another challenge lies in the available modelling tools and educational material which are rarely open-source or freely accessible. Considering these factors could significantly enhance the education of individuals studying or working in this sector.

For the successful development and delivery of the ERIGrid 2.0 educational activities, an educational strategy was introduced, as detailed in the Deliverable D4.2 (*D-NA3.1b Report on the Training Workshops and Staff Exchanges*, 2025). The goal was to align this strategy with the recommendations of the (IEEE PES Task Force on Innovative Teaching Methods for Modern Power and Energy Systems, 2024). As part of the educational strategy, the target learner groups were identified and the activities were categorised into topic areas aligned with the overall scope of ERIGrid 2.0. Lastly, the IEEE Task Force emphasises the importance of addressing different skill levels, so then, an analysis based on Bloom's taxonomy was applied ("Bloom's taxonomy: Original and revised", 2005). Thus, based on educators' feedback reports, the topics were categorised, and an assessment was conducted to evaluate skill development.

In alignment with the strategy, various e-learning resources were developed, including interactive tools, webinars, virtual and remote laboratories, as well as the ERIGrid 2.0 MOOC. Additionally, laboratory modules incorporating RTS and hardware setups were created to foster hands-on, experiential learning. Furthermore, a range of educational events was organised, such as workshops, panel sessions, tutorials, training for professionals, with special focus on high-impact activities such as training schools. The educational strategy implementation using the listed practices proved effective and was fully in line with the recommendations from (IEEE PES Task Force on Innovative Teaching Methods for Modern Power and Energy Systems, 2024).

4.2 ERIGrid 2.0 Training: Insights and Experiences

In this section, the summary of the overall experience and feedback obtained from the ERIGrid 2.0 educational activities is presented. The key points are outlined below:

- Learners demonstrated the greatest interest and satisfaction with hands-on activities and laboratory sessions. These interactive and practical experiences, which provided direct contact with equipment and software in the laboratory environment, captured participants' attention, deepened their understanding and improved their ability to retain knowledge.
- The ERIGrid 2.0 educational tools did not receive as much feedback as expected, which limited the possibility to monitor the level of engagement and fully assess their usefulness. To improve this, a more targeted approach could be followed, including the application of a user tracking system as well as links to feedback surveys.
- Comparing the feedback from the online survey on educational tools with user experience feedback from the laboratory session on Jupyter Notebooks, it becomes clear that active guidance and explanations are crucial for enhancing learning outcomes and maximising the effectiveness of the tools. To improve engagement and learning outcomes, the benefits of the online tools should be clearly communicated. Additionally, by providing step-by-step interactive guides, webinars, live demonstrations, well-structured exercises, and dedicated laboratory sessions, are recommended to ensure a more effective and hands-on learning experience.
- Dissemination of educational tools should focus on highlighting their novelty and usefulness to the users through a simple and easy-understandable message.
- A key factor for improving the usability of e-tools and enhancing user engagement is the implementation of intuitive, user-friendly interfaces with seamless navigation.
- Learners benefited most when training events followed a well-structured format, integrating theoretical foundations with practical applications. Training schools and workshops were highly valued, especially those that combined lectures with hands-on sessions. Thus, maintaining a balance between theoretical and hands-on learning is recommended.
- While students and early-career researchers benefited more from foundational and theoretical sessions, professionals and industry participants preferred advanced topics combined with real-world applications.
- Some participants expressed the need for more introductory content to address knowledge gaps, particularly in interdisciplinary topics such as cybersecurity and energy system integration. To ensure a more effective learning experience for diverse audiences, it is advisable to tailor the content and activities to the specific needs of the targeted audience. For instance, the learning paths could be structured with a beginner track focused on introducing basic concepts and foundational knowledge for students and an advanced track with industry case studies and practical applications for professionals.
- ERIGrid 2.0 aimed to obtain insight also into the gender disparity. The majority of participants and users were men and this gender imbalance reflects broader trends in STEM fields, particularly in the energy sector. It is recommended to actively promote and encourage educational activities to women through targeted outreach and conduct surveys to understand the barriers of participation.

5 Conclusions

This report summarises the e-learning tools and materials developed within ERIGrid 2.0 project and reports on the developments made during the 2nd period (M37-M59). A total of 20 resources were created, including interactive tools, virtual & remote laboratories, laboratory modules, webinars, tutorial videos, virtual lab tours, and tutorial presentations. Open-source platforms such as Zenodo¹, GitHub², YouTube³, and Moodle⁴ were used to host the developed resources, ensuring free and open access for all interested learners. Statistics on webinars and videos have also been provided, revealing thousands of views and downloads on Zenodo¹ and YouTube³ highlighting their reach and impact.

Additionally, the deliverable presents and analyses the results of an online survey designed to gather feedback on the use of the four educational tools. It also examines the responses to the customised questionnaires distributed to evaluate the use of Jupyter Notebooks during the laboratory sessions focused on power systems training. The report further presents and analyses the responses to the customized surveys used to assess two of the high-impact training schools organized within the ERIGrid 2.0 project.

The report concludes with key lessons learned and recommendations based on the overall educational and training approach followed, and on the feedback gathered from both educators and learners.

In developing the ERIGrid 2.0 educational and training approach, recommendations from the (IEEE PES Task Force on Innovative Teaching Methods for Modern Power and Energy Systems, 2024) were incorporated. A wide variety of e-learning materials was created to promote active, hands-on and practical learning and to address the interdisciplinary skills essential for the energy transition. Furthermore, Bloom's Taxonomy was employed as a standardized framework to assess the learning objectives and provide a comprehensive evaluation of the cognitive levels achieved in key areas within the scope of the ERIGrid 2.0.

In summary, the ERIGrid 2.0 educational activities received positive feedback, especially the hands-on laboratory sessions, which significantly enhanced understanding and knowledge retention. The analysis of learners' feedback revealed key lessons, emphasizing the importance of a balanced mix of theoretical and practical sessions in training events. Tailored content for diverse audiences—such as students, researchers, and professionals—was also found to be highly recommended. Furthermore, there is a clear need for more introductory content in interdisciplinary areas, along with targeted efforts to address the gender imbalance in STEM fields by encouraging and promoting a greater participation of women. These insights are demonstrating the applicability of best practices and recommendations, and are assessing their effectiveness, providing an active feedback and a clear indication for refining future educational and training directions.

References

Bloom's taxonomy: Original and revised. (2005). *Emerging perspectives on learning, teaching, and technology*, 8. Retrieved from <https://cmapspublic3.ihmc.us/rid=1FPRRBRBK-1V1PZ0J-2JPL/BloomsrevisedTaxonomy.pdf>

D-NA3.1a Report on the Training Workshops and Staff Exchanges. (2023). Deliverable D4.1, The ERIGrid 2.0 Consortium. doi:[10.5281/zenodo.7985684](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7985684)

D-NA3.1b Report on the Training Workshops and Staff Exchanges. (2025). Deliverable D4.2, The ERIGrid 2.0 Consortium. doi:[10.5281/zenodo.14746641](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14746641)

D-NA3.2 Education and Training Material for E-learning and Laboratory Education. (2023). Deliverable D4.3, The ERIGrid 2.0 Consortium. doi:[10.5281/zenodo.7987971](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7987971)

ERIGrid2/benchmark-model-multi-energy-networks: v1.0. (2021). The ERIGrid 2.0 Consortium. doi:[10.5281/zenodo.5735005](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5735005)

IEEE PES Task Force on Innovative Teaching Methods for Modern Power and Energy Systems. (2024). *Innovative teaching methods for modern power and energy systems* (Tech. Rep.). IEEE Power and Energy Society. Retrieved from https://resourcecenter.ieee-pes.org/publications/technical-reports/pes_tp_tr120_peec_032624

Appendix A: Activity Plans

A.1 Template for Activity Plan Form

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan

<Title>

Overview

Hosting partner:

Co-organizing partners:

Planned date: E.g. Summer '99 (as specific as possible)

Type of Activity:

Contact: Name, email address of person(s) filling in this form

Short Description

A description of the selection of topics, the hosting partners, intended audience and why the course is relevant to ERIGrid 2.0

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

Why is this training activity required? What specific outcomes of EG-2 are conveyed here?

Link to appropriate studies, directives, project ambition, etc.

Target group(s)

Which are the target groups meant to participate and benefit from this training activity? As specific as possible (e.g. utility, suppliers, technical staff, consultants, high-school students, general public, etc.)

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

As Training Objectives describe the competences that should be conveyed to the learners in your technical perspective. For "Workshops & Seminars" and "Panel Sessions" this section is optional.

This module intends to ...

In addition, try to specify the expected learning outcome as "Intended Learning Objectives" – specific measurable abilities that the course is intended to convey. We will use Bloom's revised taxonomy to describe the school's objective – Appendix 1 has an illustration to reference

A student who completed this course is able to:

1. e.g. Produce a coherent test description for a HIL experiment
2. ...

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Outline of Training Activity

Describe here the key components and learning activities comprising the training activity. A time schedule can be included here if available.

Evaluation approach

How is the success of the training activity evaluated? Note EG-2 requests an evaluation only by the organizers (NA3-Training_Activity_Report_Form)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Appendix 1: Formulating Learning objectives & Blooms Taxonomy
(to be deleted after completing)

The following illustration is helpful when formulating learning objectives for the Training Schools¹.

¹ Blooms taxonomy is often illustrated in levels where "Knowledge" is the most basic, followed by comprehension (against the clock in below illustration; note that in the 'Bloom's revised axonomy' the "synthesis" level has been replaced by "creating", which then was ascribed the highest level).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.2 Activity Plan Forms for Educational/Training Tools

A.2.1 Open Source Load Flow Tool in Python

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan Open Source Load Flow Tool

Overview

Hosting partner: CRES

Co-organizing partners: N/A

Planned date (approximate): July 2021

Type of Activity: Education Tool

Contact: Evangelos Rikos, vrikos@cres.gr

Short Description

A description of the selection of topics, the hosting partners, intended audience and why the course is relevant to ERIGrid 2.0

The specific tool developed by CRES aims at providing an easy and open source tool for analysis of electric power systems under steady-state conditions.

The specific tool is highly relevant to the ERIGrid 2.0 activities because, as part of the scenarios investigated in the project, analysis of power systems is very important. In addition, the analysis and use of various tools and methods for simulation/co-simulation (e.g., MOSAIK, PandaPower, etc.) make this open source tool very relevant since it has been developed in Python.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

Why is this training activity required? What specific outcomes of EG-2 are conveyed here?

Link to appropriate studies, directives, project ambition, etc.

The specific tool is useful as part of the simulation and co-simulation approaches implemented in the project. Since a large part of ERIGrid 2.0 is dedicated to the analysis of electric power systems with open source simulation and co-simulation platforms, the specific tool is a good example towards this direction.

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

As Training Objectives Describe the competences that should be conveyed to the learners in your technical perspective.

This module intends to familiarize the user with two aspects:

- Modelling and analysis of electric power systems under steady-state conditions and

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

- Implementation of open source code for this analysis with possibility of extending its functionalities and data interchanges with other tools

In addition, try to specify the expected learning outcome as “Intended Learning Objectives” – specific measurable abilities that the course is intended to convey. We will use Bloom’s revised taxonomy to describe the school’s objective – Appendix 1 has an illustration to reference

A student who completed this course is able to:

1. Implement a consistent steady-state (Load Flow) analysis for specific power system examples
2. Expand the tool’s functionalities towards adding more features (e.g., a Graphical User Interface, implementation in multiple timeframes, interfacing with other tools, etc.)

Outline of Training Activity

Describe here the key components and learning activities comprising the training activity. A time schedule can be included here if available.

The code for the tool is developed in Python3.6.4 and is structured in the form shown in the following diagram:

The structure of the tool is divided into three parts, one related to the input data files in txt format, one containing the Python libraries that execute the Load Flow analysis, and one containing the output data, also in txt format. The user can introduce the specific power system model parameters through the input data, which cover a variety of aspects such as Grid Parameters, Initial Voltages, etc.

Evaluation approach

How is the success of the training activity evaluated? Note EG-2 requests an evaluation only by the organizers (NA3-Training_Activity_Report_Form)

The success of the tool could be evaluated by the number of users/downloads of the source code.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.2.2 Power Flow Jupyter Notebooks

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan < Power Flow Jupyter Notebooks >

Overview

Hosting partner: ICCS-NTUA

Co-organizing partners: -

Planned date (approximate): December 2021/2022

Type of Activity: Laboratory Exercise for undergraduate students

Contact: Alkistis Kontou (alkistiskont@gmail.com)

Short Description

The power flow problem in Jupyter Notebooks was integrated in the first laboratory exercise of Power System Analysis (Steady State) Course in the 8th semester of the School of Electrical and Computer Engineering at National Technical University of Athens.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

Using the Jupyter notebook structure, the implemented mathematical process is theoretically explained at each step of the source code. Additionally, the results are presented at the end of each step along with some graphics for the voltage, the active and reactive power of the buses.

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

As Training Objectives Describe the competences that should be conveyed to the learners in your technical perspective.

This module intends to:

1. Familiarize students with the mathematical process for the power flow calculation and solving
2. Analyze the operation of power systems under steady-state
3. Familiarize students with useful programming tools like Jupyter Notebooks.

In addition, try to specify the expected learning outcome as “Intended Learning Objectives” – specific measurable abilities that the course is intended to convey. We will use Bloom’s revised taxonomy to describe the school’s objective – Appendix 1 has an illustration to reference

A student who completed this course is able to:

1. Formulate the mathematical equations of the power flow problem
2. Record the calculations of the power flow problem
3. Assess the results of the power flow problem

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Outline of Training Activity

In the first part, students are introduced to Jupyter Notebooks platform. Following this presentation, the participants upload and run the Power flow-Jupyter source file to the platform step by step. In the Ybus step, they are required to fill in the missing part of the code for the formulation of the matrix. Additionally, they fill in and submit a questionnaire with the results of each step of the power flow problem.

Evaluation approach

A questionnaire has been prepared to receive feedback from students. The participants expressed their view anonymously by evaluating topics such as content, relevance of the exercise with the course, presentation and implementation of the exercise and utility, using the 0-5 scale.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.2.3 Energy Analysis Tool for Microgrid and Islanded Systems

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan

Energy Analysis Tool for Microgrid and Islanded Power Systems

Overview

Hosting partner: CRES

Co-organizing partners: N/A

Planned date (approximate): July 2021

Type of Activity: Education Tool

Contact: Evangelos Rikos, vrikos@cres.gr

Short Description

A description of the selection of topics, the hosting partners, intended audience and why the course is relevant to ERIGrid 2.0

This is a free license tool, which allows users to simulate the energy behavior of a microgrid or an autonomous power system under steady-state conditions.

The specific tool is highly relevant to the ERIGrid 2.0 because of the scenarios that are analyzed in the project. These scenarios emphasize a lot on the case of microgrids, whereas other scenarios investigated in the project, including energy communities, make the use of the specific tool highly relevant.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

Why is this training activity required? What specific outcomes of EG-2 are conveyed here?

Link to appropriate studies, directives, project ambition, etc.

The specific tool is useful as part of the simulation and co-simulation approaches implemented in the project. Since a large part of ERIGrid 2.0 is dedicated to the analysis of microgrids and distribution grids, the use of such a tool is highly relevant and important.

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

As Training Objectives Describe the competences that should be conveyed to the learners in your technical perspective.

This module intends to familiarize the user with two aspects:

- Modelling and analysis of microgrids and autonomous power systems under steady-state conditions and

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

- Optimization of the system’s operation in terms of cost and Renewable Generation.

In addition, try to specify the expected learning outcome as “Intended Learning Objectives” – specific measurable abilities that the course is intended to convey. We will use Bloom’s revised taxonomy to describe the school’s objective – Appendix 1 has an illustration to reference

A student who completed this course is able to:

1. Understand the techno-economic aspects of microgrids and autonomous power systems such as the power systems of geographical islands
2. Implement this analysis in the simulation environment and obtain the necessary results

Outline of Training Activity

Describe here the key components and learning activities comprising the training activity. A time schedule can be included here if available.

The specific tool is provided in the form of an executable application that allows the user to design the microgrid topology via a Graphical Interface:

Through this interface environment the user can introduce specific resources and specify their parameters. Also, other scenario parameters can be introduced via this interface. The execution of the simulation tests provide specific results illustrated in separate screens such as the one below:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Results can also be exported in the form of data files for further processing.

Evaluation approach

How is the success of the training activity evaluated? Note EG-2 requests an evaluation only by the organizers (NA3-Training_Activity_Report_Form)

The success of the tool could be evaluated by the number of users/downloads of the application.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.2.4 Smart Grid Applications Leveraging Machine Learning Principles

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan

Smart grid applications leveraging machine learning principles in R studio

Overview

Hosting partner: University of Cyprus (UCY) - FOSS Research Centre for Sustainable Energy

Co-organizing partners: -

Planned date (approximate): Autumn 2022

Type of Activity: Education tool

Contact: George Makrides, makrides.georgios@ucy.ac.cy

Short Description

The smart grid applications leveraging machine learning principles in R studio is an educational tool relevant to the topics of predicting the performance of solar photovoltaic systems and forecasting day-ahead generation leveraging advanced artificial intelligent (AI) principles. Specifically, it presents the use of data-driven machine learning principles for the implementation of solar-specific smart grid applications (digital twin predictive performance models and solar generation forecasting). A detailed step-by-step procedure is provided for the construction of high-performing data-driven predictive models for photovoltaic (PV) systems based on a supervised learning approach and leveraging different machine learning techniques (artificial neural networks, support vector regression, regression trees, etc.). The predictive models (derived using the R scripting statistical computing programming language) are benchmarked and optimized by varying the input features, learning regime and model hyperparameters. Finally, the application of the constructed models as a PV power plant digital twin (optimally performing virtual replica) and in solar generation forecasting (day- and hour-ahead forecasting) is verified using actual PV performance datasets and numerical weather predictions (NWP).

Hosting partner: UCY- FOSS Research Centre for Sustainable Energy.

Intended audience: Researchers in the fields of solar production forecasting and AI modeling for smart grid applications.

Lastly, the course is relevant to ERIGrid 2.0 since it provides the demonstration environment of smart grid concepts pertaining to renewable system digital twins, solar generation forecasting and application of AI-driven approaches in the smart grid domain.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

The motivation behind this educational tool is the transition towards a secure, cost-effective and environmentally sustainable energy supply by enhancing the innovation landscape for optimally planning and operating future grids using day-ahead forecasting as a key and cost-effective enabler. The educational tool thereby aligns to this trend by providing the demonstration environment for key enabling technologies such as AI-driven solar generation forecasting.

The specific outcomes of EG-2 conveyed include the:

- Validation of predictive models leveraging machine learning principles for digital twin modeling
- Demonstration of an accurately performing AI-driven day-ahead solar generation forecasting tool

Transitioning to a sustainable energy society and mitigating climate change effects through accelerated energy sector decarbonization is a recognised top priority of the European Union (EU) under the recent European Green Deal (EGD) climate-neutral initiatives to reduce emissions by at least 55% by 2030.

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

This tool intends to:

- Design data-driven digital twin models for solar PV systems
- Apply NWP data and AI-driven principles for hour- and day-ahead generation forecasting
- Validate the performance of different machine learning techniques in digital twin modeling
- Demonstrate the performance of AI technologies for day- and hour-ahead solar PV production applications

A student who completed this course is able to:

1. Produce a coherent PV power plant digital twin predictive model
2. Examine historic PV production data and validate the performance of the predictive model
3. Comprehend the underlying configuration structures of AI-driven principles for solar generation forecasting

Outline of Training Activity

The key components of this educational tool include the predictive modeling framework and the demonstration of day- and hour-ahead PV production forecasting based on AI-driven principles.

The learning activities comprise of:

- Setup of PV power plant predictive model
- benchmarking of machine learning techniques for PV plant digital twin modeling
- Design of solar PV production forecasting tool
- Verification of tool based on historic PV power plant data

Evaluation approach

The success of the training activity will be evaluated by obtaining feedback from the participants through the completion of an evaluation questionnaire.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.3 Activity Plan Forms for Webinars

A.3.1 Remote Testing & EIRIE Platform

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Report Remote Testing & EIRIE Platform

Overview

Hosting partner: DERlab

Co-organizing partners: University of Strathclyde, AIT, TECNALIA, DTU, RWTH, ICCS-NTUA, FOSS

Delivered date: 08 March 2021

Type of Activity: Webinar

Contact: leonard.ramos@der-lab.net

Agenda and Schedule of the event

- Welcome words from DERlab Board (Graeme Burt, Mohamed Shalaby)
- Overview of the ERIGrid 2.0 Research Infrastructure for Smart Grids and Smart Energy Systems (AIT / Thomas Strasser)
- Introduction of the ERIGrid 2.0 Lab Access Programme (TECNALIA / J. Emilio Rodriguez Seco)
- Experiences with Remote Lab Access Services on the Example VILLAS4ERIGrid (DTU / Kai Heussen)
- Virtual Research Services in ERIGrid 2.0 (RWTH Aachen / Steffen Vogel)
- Demo of the VLab Services from RWTH Aachen (RWTH Aachen / Steffen Vogel)
- Demo of the OpenAFPM Services from ICCS-NTUA (ICCS-NTUA / Kostas Latoufis)
- PANTERA project - A pan European Technology Energy Research Approach (FOSS / Venizelos Efthymiou)
- Q&A (DERlab / Mohamed Shalaby)

List of participants

List of participants		
Mohamed Shalaby	Maria Robowska	Isabel Alvite
Thomas Strasser	Felipe Jung	Tran-The Hoang
Shafi Khadem	Benedikt Leitner	Maria Trifiletti
Christina Papadimitriou	Artjoms Obusevs	Changhee Cho
Lorena Sánchez Relaño	Darshan Gab'ndhi	Antonello Monti
Anna Mutule	Amelia Alvarez de Sotomayor	Marta Sturzeanu
Alexandros Tsitsanis	M Moiz	otilia bularca
Tasos Tsitsanis	Ahmad Niazi	Sophia Giovanett
Maria-Iro Baka	Vasileios Psaras	Rainer Bacher
Paula Carroll	Rais Mohamed Cherif	Guillaume GIRAUD
Theofilos Papadopoulos	Alexis Rey-Boué	Dagmar Jarasová

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Nikola Celanovic
Mahdieh Sadabadi
Georgios Mitrentsis

Mikhail Khokhlov

Simon Stock
Athanasios Krontiris
Jochen Kreusel

Inaki Orue
Eduardo Vega Fuentes
Sobhan Naderian
Rad Stanev

JOSE FERNANDO FORERO
QUINTERO

Abdulrahman BABAGANA
Gerd Heilscher

Asma Aziz
Andreas Armenakis
Farhad Safargholi

Efren Guillo
Ivan Morar
Sergio Costa

BERNARD ISTASSE

Ibrahim Abdulhadi
Hazem Karbouj

Svitlana Kolosok

Maria-Iro Baka

Loizos Loizou
Björn Machill

Jorge Bracho
Julia Chenut
Dorothea Brockhoff
Elisabeth Mrakotsky

Till Neukamp

Nuno S Silva
Rad Stanev

Graeme Burt
Jean Patric da Costa
Carlo Mol

Riccardo Lazzari
IOULIA PAPAIOANNOU
Marcin Tarasiuk

David Veltmann

Dagmar Jarásová

Alicia Kalms

Juan Manuel González
Sopeña

Sophia Pfeffer

Andrei Morch

Enea Bionda

Carlo Tornelli

Steffen Vogel

Carina Zidaru

Katerina Maxouti

Kyriaki Psara

Kostas Latoufis

Mattia Cabiati

Asia Codino

Irina Antoskova

Justice Chihota

Rohit Trivedi

Adam Babá

Mario Dionisio

Short description of the event activities/ Presented topics of the event

ERIGrid 2.0 partners showcased the project's infrastructure and present the collected experiences with remote lab access. Also presented were the ERIGrid 2.0 Virtual Access to infrastructures with demos of two virtual facilities.

The PANTERA project presented the interactive multi-functional platform EIRIE that acts as the meeting point of all actors active in the field of energy research and innovation from all Europe.

Achievements and learning outcomes

Participants familiarized themselves with the scope of the ERIGrid 2.0 project, its Lab Access and Virtual Access programmes and their available physical and virtual facilities. The participants were able to witness the real-time demonstrations of two virtual services.

In addition, the participants were introduced to the PANTERA project, its objectives and the planned outcomes of the project.

To sum up, the participants were presented the scope of the projects and the opportunities they provide to the smart energy community. The participants also had the possibility to clarify any questions in the Q&A session, which was a valuable opportunity for potential ERIGrid 2.0 Lab Access applicants.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Statistics of the event (Webinars or Virtual Workshops)

- No. of registered persons: 169
- No. of attendees: 93
- No. of project external persons: 79

[Webinar Recording on YouTube](#)

Feedback from participants (For activities that distributed questionnaires to participants)

In case a questionnaire was distributed to participants, please provide the results.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.3.2 Recent Research Trends in Engineering and Validating Cyber-Physical Energy Systems

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan

Recent Research Trends in Engineering and Validating Cyber-Physical Energy Systems

Overview

Hosting partner: AIT

Co-organizing partners: IEEE Industrial Electronics Society (IES)

Planned date: 29.06.2021

Type of Activity: Webinar (in the IES webinar series)

Contact: Thomas Strasser, thomas.strasser@ait.ac.at; Filip Pröstitl Andrén, filip.proestl-andren@ait.ac.at

Short Description

A driving force for the realization of a sustainable energy supply is the integration of renewable energy resources. Due to their stochastic generation behaviour, energy utilities are confronted with a more complex operation of the underlying power grids. Additionally, due to technology developments, controllable loads, integration with other energy sources, changing regulatory rules, and the market liberalization, the system's operation needs adaptation. Proper operational concepts and intelligent automation provide the basis to turn the existing power system into an intelligent entity, a cyber-physical energy system. The electric energy system is therefore moving from a single system to a system of systems.

While reaping the benefits with new intelligent behaviours, it is expected that system-level developments, architectural concepts, advanced automation and control as well as the validation and testing will play a significantly larger role in realizing future solutions and technologies. The implementation and deployment of these complex systems of systems are associated with increasing engineering complexity resulting also in increased engineering costs. Proper engineering and validation approaches and tools are partly missing until now.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

This webinar that is held by the IEEE IES discusses and summarizes the main needs and requirements as well as the status quo in research and development related to the engineering and validation of cyber-physical energy systems. Also, validation examples and short demos are presented. Finally, research trends and necessary future activities are outlined.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Target group(s)

All ERIGRID 2.0 stakeholders (academia/research, industry, energy utilities, standardization, general public).

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

This module intends to show future energy systems' higher complexity in scenarios with different penetration levels of renewables. It also introduces the necessity of system-level design and validation approaches based on simulations and laboratory testing as well as the combination of them in a hardware-in-the-loop manner.

Outline of Training Activity

The webinar covers the following topics:

- Higher complexity in cyber-physical energy systems
- Engineering problems and needs
- Status quo in research and development
- Validating controllers for cyber-physical energy systems
- Example Demo

Evaluation approach

An evaluation of the webinar is planned by IEEE IES in the form of an online questionnaire.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.3.3 Mosaik 3.0 - Open-Source Smart Grid Co-simulation Framework

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan <Mosaik 3.0>

Overview

Hosting partner: OFFIS
 Co-organizing partners: -
 Planned date (approximate): September 2021
 Type of Activity: Webinar
 Contact: Jirapa Kamsamrong (jirapa.kamsamrong@offis.de)

Short Description

Nowadays, co-simulation is a very useful tool to combine detailed models of different domains for multi-modal analyses, to integrate components with different software stacks, and to split the computational load of simulations between several machines. Among different all-purpose co-simulation frameworks, the open-source tool mosaik is special in the way that it focuses on high usability and simple simulation setups. However, some use cases, especially the combination of continuous dynamics with discrete events (e.g. cyber-physical systems that rely on communication), couldn't be supported efficiently. Mosaik 3.0 can support these hybrid scenarios, superdense time, and many other things with minimal interface adjustments.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

Smart grid incorporates different domains and multi-energy networks. To combined different simulations, Mosaik enables to reuse and combine existing simulation models and simulators to create large-scale Smart Grid scenarios. These scenarios can then serve as a testbed for various types of control strategies or other algorithmic solutions for future power systems. According to ERGrid 2 project objectives, it aims to support the research, technology development, and innovation of smart grid and smart energy system approaches. Especially, the working activity in ERIGrid 2 project of JRA 1 that aims to establish the reference scenarios for validations and upscaling and JRA2 to improve interconnecting (coupling) multiple instances of non-real-time simulators, real-time simulators, hardware-in-the-loop components, and physical laboratory equipment.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Hence, the holistic system integration and testing procedure can be performed by using co-simulation software. Mosaik is well-known among researchers and students for co-simulation platforms from a basic scenarios to sophisticated scenarios. The new release Mosaik 3.0 offers new features to improve discrete-event capabilities. This would allow both internal ERIGRID partners and external interested users for adapting the new features to their research. Therefore, the “New co-simulation features of Mosaik 3.0” webinar will introduce new features of Mosaik for interested users.

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

This module intends to introduce new features of Mosaik co-simulation that aim for intended learning for interested users that have basic knowledge and experience with Mosaik. The expected learning outcome is the learners will obtain new features during the webinar with simple examples and demos. The participants are expected to adopt new features by themselves depending on the context starting from the synthesis of their problems and adapting to their models/research. In addition, Mosaik developers (i.e. presenters at the webinar) also provide support via <https://mosaik.offis.de/contact/> for further questions after the event.

A student who completed this course is able to:

- Intermediate and advanced participants can apply new features of Mosaik 3.0 to their work
- Basic users understand how to work with Mosaik 3.0

Outline of Training Activity

- Introduction of mosaik (including new mosaik 3.0 features)
- Tutorial and demos showing new mosaik 3.0 features
- Questions

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.3.4 Addressing the Growing Complexity of Power and Energy Systems through Interconnection of Geographically Distributed Research Laboratories

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan

14-05-2023

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan

Addressing the Growing Complexity of Power and Energy Systems through Interconnection of Geographically Distributed Research Laboratories

Overview

Hosting partner: University of Strathclyde (UoS)
Co-organizing partners: impossible

Planned date (approximate): 24/May/2022

Type of Activity: Webinar

Contact: Zhiwang Feng and Mazher Syed, zhiwang.feng@strath.ac.uk

Short Description

A description of the selection of topics, the hosting partners, intended audience and why the course is relevant to ERIGrid 2.0

This webinar titled “Addressing the Growing Complexity of Power and Energy Systems through Interconnection of Geographically Distributed Research Laboratories” will be delivered by Dr. Mazher Syed (UoS) as part of the Smart Grid Webinar Series 2022 organized by Smart Grid Operation Centre, IVE Engineering, Hong Kong.

The intended audience include (but are not limited to) students, academic researchers, and industrial engineers working on power system controls, real-time simulations and experimental validations.

This seminar will disseminate the research work undertaken as part of Task JRA2.2 of the ERIGrid 2.0 project.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

Why is this training activity required? What specific outcomes of EG-2 are conveyed here?
Link to appropriate studies, directives, project ambition, etc.

The limitations of a single research infrastructure to address the growing complexity of power and energy systems has been quite evident in the recent past. While geographically distributed simulations approach has been proposed as a potential solution, its recognition and adoption is quite limited. This seminar demonstrates the applicability and feasibility of geographically distributed real-time simulation techniques for the validation of complex power systems. The developments and advancements in

1

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan

14-05-2023

enabling the optimized utilization of the real-time validation capabilities of the geographically distributed research laboratories realised within ERIGrid 2.0 project will be disseminated. This research outcome is a key enabler for addressing the simulation limitation of the single research infrastructure in investigating the power energy system with growing complexity.

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Objectives (ILOs)

As Training Objectives Describe the competences that should be conveyed to the learners in your technical perspective.

- To inform of the state-of-the-art developments and breakthroughs in geographically distributed real-time simulations to support validation of complex power and energy systems.
- Demonstrate applications of techniques with real-world examples.

In addition, try to specify the expected learning outcome as “Intended Learning Objectives” – specific measurable abilities that the course is intended to convey. We will use Bloom’s revised taxonomy to describe the school’s objective – Appendix 1 has an illustration to reference

An audience that has attended this panel session will be able to:

- **Beginners:** Describe, discuss and relate to geographically distributed real-time simulation techniques: their functionality, applicability, and suitability for validation of complex power and energy systems.
- **Intermediate:** Identify scenarios where the presented techniques can be employed.
- **Expert:** Employ techniques for validation of complex power and energy systems.
- **Expert:** Criticize and propose advances to techniques through further research.

Outline of Training Activity

Describe here the key components and learning activities comprising the training activity. A time schedule can be included here if available.

This activity will be carried out in the form of a webinar as part of the Smart Grid Webinar Series 2022 organized by Smart Grid Operation Centre, IVE Engineering, Hong Kong. A brief outline of the webinar is presented below:

- A summary of modern power grid transformation and challenges
- An introduction of geographically distributed simulations (GDS)
- Taxonomy and examples of GDS
- Demonstration of current developments

Evaluation approach

How is the success of the training activity evaluated? Note EG-2 requests an evaluation only by the organisers (NA3-TrainingActivity-Feedback-Form)

No formal evaluation is planned, however, a qualitative assessment through audience participation and engagement can be undertaken.

2

A.3.5 First Webinar of RICH Europe on Transnational and Virtual access opportunities TA/VA

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan

First Webinar of RICH Europe on Transnational and Virtual access opportunities (TA/VA)

Overview

Hosting partner: AIT

Co-organizing partners: HEU RICH Europe CSA RI Project of NCPs

Planned date: 23.11.2022

Type of Activity: Webinar

Contact: Thomas Strasser, thomas.strasser@ait.ac.at

Short Description

Introduction and overview of the ERIGrid 2.0 validation, testing, and education services with a focus on the access program to potential access users.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

The training is required to provide general information about the project as well as the access program to potential access users.

Target group(s)

All ERIGrid 2.0 stakeholders (academia/research, industry, energy utilities, standardization, general public) with a focus on potential access users.

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

This module intends to show the higher complexity of future energy systems and introduces the necessity of system-level design and validation approaches based on simulations and laboratory testing as well as the combination of it in a hardware-in-the-loop manner. Furthermore, details about the access program and how to apply for it are provided.

Outline of Training Activity

The activity consists of a brief overview presentation with a focus on the access program.

Evaluation approach

No evaluation is foreseen.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.4 Activity Plan Forms for Virtual and Remote Labs

A.4.1 Solar-plus- storage system environmental and performance measurements

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan

Virtual access to solar-plus-storage system environmental and performance measurements

Overview

Hosting partner: University of Cyprus (UCY) - FOSS Research Centre for Sustainable Energy

Co-organizing partners: -

Planned date (approximate): Autumn 2022

Type of Activity: Virtual Labs

Contact: George Makrides, makrides.georgios@ucy.ac.cy

Short Description

The solar-plus-storage system environmental and performance measurements virtual lab is an educational training activity relevant to the topics of distributed energy resource observability (solar photovoltaic and battery storage systems), digitalization of grid assets and real-time supervision using grid-edge programmable automation controllers and cloud-based interfaces. Specifically, it presents an overview of the performance and supervisory architecture, leveraging cloud-based system dashboards that stream real-time (1-sec resolution) data, for a smart photovoltaic and battery storage test-bench system installed at UCY microgrid. The acquired smart meter measurements (using Modbus TCP SunSpec protocols) include the voltage, frequency, power (apparent, active and reactive), inverter temperature, charging/discharging power and operational status of the solar-plus-storage system.

Hosting partner: UCY- FOSS Research Centre for Sustainable Energy.

Intended audience: Researchers in the fields of solar-plus-storage systems and grid modernization.

Lastly, the course is relevant to ERIGrid 2.0 since it provides the demonstration environment of smart grid concepts pertaining to real-time distributed energy resource observability using smart inverters and open-communication interoperability in smart grids.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

The motivation behind this activity is the transition towards a secure, cost-effective and environmentally sustainable energy supply by enhancing the innovation landscape for integrating renewable energy sources. The training activity thereby aligns to this trend by providing the demonstration environment for

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Transitioning to a sustainable energy society and mitigating climate change effects through accelerated energy sector decarbonization is a recognised top priority of the European Union (EU) under the recent European Green Deal (EGD) climate-neutral initiatives to reduce emissions by at least 55% by 2030.

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

This module intends to:

- Design a cloud-based supervision system for solar-plus-storage systems
- Apply open-communication interoperability protocols to stream data from grid-edge devices
- Validate advanced controls for smart inverters
- Demonstrate the performance of programmable automation devices linked to cloud databases for grid asset observability

A student who completed this course is able to:

1. Produce a coherent architecture for the real-time observability of solar-plus-storage systems
2. Examine historic consumption and production data of the solar-plus-storage system
3. Comprehend the underlying configuration structures of automation controllers that leverage interoperability in smart grids

Outline of Training Activity

The key components of this training activity include the interoperability framework, architectural design and demonstration of the solar-plus-storage cloud-based supervisory system.

The learning activities comprise of:

- Setup of photovoltaic and battery storage smart inverter for open communications
- Configuration of a programmable automation device to connect to specific registers of the inverters
- Design of cloud-based databases and dashboards for the visualization of real-time data streams
- Validation of supervisory data streams and advanced controls

Evaluation approach

The success of the training activity will be evaluated by obtaining feedback from the participants through the completion of an evaluation questionnaire.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.4.2 UCY microgrid real-time measurements

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan

Virtual access to UCY microgrid real-time measurements

Overview

Hosting partner: University of Cyprus (UCY) - FOSS Research Centre for Sustainable Energy

Co-organizing partners: -

Planned date (approximate): Autumn 2022

Type of Activity: Virtual Labs

Contact: George Makrides, makrides.georgios@ucy.ac.cy

Short Description

The microgrid real-time measurements virtual lab is an educational training activity relevant to the topics of smart meter data acquisition in microgrids, distributed energy resource observability (solar photovoltaic and battery storage systems), digitalization of grid assets and real-time supervision using grid-edge programmable automation controllers and cloud-based interfaces. Specifically, it presents an overview of the supervisory architecture, leveraging cloud-based system dashboards that stream real-time (1-sec resolution) data, from smart meters installed within a commercial-scale microgrid, UCY microgrid. The acquired smart meter measurements (using Modbus TCP SunSpec protocols) include the voltage, frequency, power (apparent, active and reactive) and power quality parameters (total harmonic distortion and crest factors). Measurements of solar irradiance, wind speed and direction, and temperature from a smart weather station are also coupled to the data streams.

Hosting partner: UCY- FOSS Research Centre for Sustainable Energy.

Intended audience: Researchers in the fields of microgrids and grid modernization.

Lastly, the course is relevant to ERIGrid 2.0 since it provides the demonstration environment of smart grid concepts pertaining to real-time distributed energy resource observability using smart meters and open-communication interoperability in smart grids.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

The motivation behind this activity is the transition towards a secure, cost-effective and environmentally sustainable energy supply by enhancing the innovation landscape for balancing demand and generation through microgrids. The training activity thereby aligns to this trend by providing the demonstration environment for key enabling technologies such as battery storage systems and grid-edge asset digitalization for solar-powered microgrids.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

- Validation of smart grid asset digitalization for real-time supervision
- Demonstration of a novel cloud-based tools for real-time observability

Transitioning to a sustainable energy society and mitigating climate change effects through accelerated energy sector decarbonization is a recognised top priority of the European Union (EU) under the recent European Green Deal (EGD) climate-neutral initiatives to reduce emissions by at least 55% by 2030.

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

This module intends to:

- Design a cloud-based supervision system for microgrids
- Apply open-communication interoperability protocols to stream data from grid-edge devices
- Validate advanced controls for smart inverters
- Demonstrate the performance of programmable automation devices linked to cloud databases for grid asset observability

A student who completed this course is able to:

1. Produce a coherent architecture for the real-time observability of the microgrid
2. Examine historic consumption and production data of the microgrid
3. Comprehend the underlying configuration structures of automation controllers that leverage interoperability in smart grids

Outline of Training Activity

The key components of this training activity include the interoperability framework, architectural design and demonstration of the microgrid cloud-based supervisory system.

The learning activities comprise of:

- Setup of smart meters for open communications
- Configuration of a programmable automation device to connect to specific registers of the smart meters
- Design of cloud-based databases and dashboards for the visualization of real-time data streams
- Validation of supervisory data streams and advanced controls

Evaluation approach

The success of the training activity will be evaluated by obtaining feedback from the participants through the completion of an evaluation questionnaire.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.4.3 Environmental measurements and PV models

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan

Virtual Access to Environmental Measurements and PV Models

Overview

Hosting partner: CRES

Co-organizing partners: N/A

Planned date (approximate): March 2022

Type of Activity: Education Tool

Contact: Evangelos Rikos, vrikos@cres.gr

Short Description

A description of the selection of topics, the hosting partners, intended audience and why the course is relevant to ERIGrid 2.0

The specific tool provides access to a set of environmental and operational data from the PV systems located on the CRES premises in Pikermi, Greece.

The use of this tool is very relevant to the ERIGrid 2.0 activities, especially the activities under the VA work package as well as the JRA activities that address the Data-as-a-Service topic.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

Why is this training activity required? What specific outcomes of EG-2 are conveyed here?

Link to appropriate studies, directives, project ambition, etc.

This tool familiarizes the user with the operating characteristics of PV systems in relation to the environmental conditions. Apart from the online access to data, the user can benefit from downloading time series data in *.csv format for post processing or use in other applications.

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

As Training Objectives Describe the competences that should be conveyed to the learners in your technical perspective.

This module intends to familiarize the user with understanding the operating characteristics of PV systems under different environmental conditions.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

In addition, try to specify the expected learning outcome as “Intended Learning Objectives” – specific measurable abilities that the course is intended to convey. We will use Bloom’s revised taxonomy to describe the school’s objective – Appendix 1 has an illustration to reference

A student who completes this course is able to:

1. Understand the operating characteristics of PV systems under real conditions,
2. Further analyze data related to the PV operation.

Outline of Training Activity

Describe here the key components and learning activities comprising the training activity. A time schedule can be included here if available.

The specific tool is divided into the physical setup and the web interface. The physical setup, involves two PV systems installed at different locations at CRES as can be seen in the following picture:

Also, the meteorological data are provided by an experimental setup used for the long-term assessment of PV modules. This setup and the relevant sensors are shown in the following figure:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

The data are collected by a data logger and published online on a webpage. A screenshot of part of this webpage is shown below:

PV System At CRES's Parking Lot

The measurements concern a PV system of 4.845kWp system which is installed in a parking lot of CRES, at a tilt of 40° and South orientation.

(Drag an area for zoom, right click to reset. Measurements of a chart can be downloaded by clicking on the legend of the chart.)

Choose time period:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Evaluation approach

How is the success of the training activity evaluated? Note EG-2 requests an evaluation only by the organizers (NA3-Training_Activity_Report_Form)

Evaluation of the specific tool's success can be achieved by monitoring the visibility of the specific webpage

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.4.4 Microgrid balancing experiment

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan Remote Access to Microgrid Balancing Experiment

Overview

Hosting partner: CRES

Co-organizing partners: N/A

Planned date (approximate): February 2022

Type of Activity: Education Tool

Contact: Evangelos Rikos, vrikos@cres.gr

Short Description

A description of the selection of topics, the hosting partners, intended audience and why the course is relevant to ERIGrid 2.0

The specific tool is a laboratory exercise that involves the remote connection to the experimental microgrid of CRES, with the aim of conducting a simplified power balancing experiment.

The relevance of the specific tool to the ERIGrid 2.0 activities arises from two aspects: Firstly, the scenarios investigated by ERIGrid 2.0 include, to a large extent, microgrids, and thus, experimentation on a microgrid is very relevant. In addition, and this is the second aspect that makes this tool highly relevant, the remote use of RIs by users is one of the key aspects of the project, connected to the extended RI analysis. Towards this direction, the remote lab application by CRES provides useful insights to the project partners and third parties.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

Why is this training activity required? What specific outcomes of EG-2 are conveyed here?

Link to appropriate studies, directives, project ambition, etc.

The specific tool is useful as part of the ERIGrid 2.0 activities connected to VA and TA activities, as well as JRA activities that deal with the extended RI (remote lab connections, services, and applications). This activity allows the host RI to prepare the laboratory for connecting with other laboratories of the consortium and allows potential external users (TA applicants) to become familiar with the specific RI and motivate them towards using it through the TA activity.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

As Training Objectives Describe the competences that should be conveyed to the learners in your technical perspective.

This module intends to familiarize users with two aspects:

- Experimentation on the power balancing of microgrids
- Understanding and use of tools that enable the remote access to laboratories and, overall, the Internet-of-Things concept

In addition, try to specify the expected learning outcome as “Intended Learning Objectives” – specific measurable abilities that the course is intended to convey. We will use Bloom’s revised taxonomy to describe the school’s objective – Appendix 1 has an illustration to reference

A student who completed this course is able to:

1. Understand the operating characteristics of microgrids and balancing requirements
2. Understand and implement the toolset that enables the access and control to a facility that is part of the Internet-of-Things concept

Outline of Training Activity

Describe here the key components and learning activities comprising the training activity. A time schedule can be included here if available.

The specific tool is divided into the physical setup and the web interface. The physical setup, which is located at the CRES premises in Pikermi, Greece, is shown in the following figure:

As can be seen in the simplified diagram, the two types of power units used in this experiment are Photovoltaics and Battery Storage. The scope of the experiment is that the user should manually modify the active power set-point of the storage unit in order to balance the production from the PVs. In addition to the active power set-point, the user can activate or deactivate the PVs, when necessary and to adjust the reactive power of the Battery Inverter in order to allow for more available power capacity.

The Battery Inverter communicates with the central SCADA application (in Node-RED) via RS485/SMANet, whereas, for the operation/supervision of the PVs two ESP32 controllers are utilized. The latter controllers connect to the SCADA application via wifi access. Both the Battery Inverter and the ESP32 modules use MQTT in order to publish their data to a specific broker, which, in turn, communicates with the SCADA over the LAN. Inversely, control quantities from the SCADA are published to the same broker, and the DER units of the microgrid, functioning as subscribers, are

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

The remote user of the experiment can supervise and control the setup via the following web interface:

Evaluation approach

How is the success of the training activity evaluated? Note EG-2 requests an evaluation only by the organizers (NA3-Training_Activity_Report_Form)

Since this experiment involves actual laboratory equipment exposed on the Internet, the strategy followed is to be available only upon request. Therefore, the requests received via email will be the precise approach to evaluate the success of the specific tool.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.5 Activity Plan Forms for Other E-Learning Material

A.5.1 Video: About ERIGrid 2.0 – Connecting European Smart Grid RIs

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan General Project Introduction

Overview

Hosting partner: AIT

Co-organizing partners: ---

Planned date: 17.11.2020 (update/extension on 21.11.2020)

Type of Activity: Video(s)

Contact: Thomas Strasser, thomas.strasser@ait.ac.at

Short Description

Introduction and overview of the ERIGrid 2.0 validation, testing, and education services provided by the coordinator AIT to the general public.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

The training is required to provide general information to the public in the form of a video.

Target group(s)

All ERIGrid 2.0 stakeholders (academia/research, industry, energy utilities, standardization, general public).

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

This module intends to show future energy systems' higher complexity in scenarios with different penetration levels of renewables. It also introduces the necessity of system-level design and validation approaches based on simulations and laboratory testing as well as the combination of them in a hardware-in-the-loop manner. It also introduces the access activities of the project.

Outline of Training Activity

The activity consists of a brief overview video.

Evaluation approach

No evaluation is foreseen.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.5.2 Virtual Lab Tour through the SysTec Lab

ERIGRID 2.0 Training Activity Report Virtual Lab Tour Fraunhofer IEE SysTec

Overview

Hosting partner: Fraunhofer IEE

Co-organizing partners: internal - ; external: Kassel University, Fraunhofer ISE and University of Freiburg

Delivered date: 2021-09-22

Type of Activity: Virtual Laboratory Tour through the test center SysTec of Fraunhofer IEE

Contact: Dr. Gunter Arnold, gunter.arnold@iee.fraunhofer.de

Agenda and Schedule of the event

The Virtual Laboratory Tour through the test center SysTec of Fraunhofer IEE was part of the “Wind and Solar Synergy Week” primarily organised by Fraunhofer IEE, Fraunhofer ISE and the Universities of Kassel and Freiburg for Master students of the “Online MSc. Wind Energy Systems and Solar Energy Engineering”. The virtual lab tour was scheduled for around 1.5 h and took place on Wed. 22. Sept. 2022 at 4 pm CEST.

List of participants (Only for Summer/Winter schools and workshops)

Not available

Short description of the event activities/ Presented topics of the event

The virtual lab tour provided a brief overview of different testing facilities at the test center SysTec located at Fraunhofer IEE, Kassel / Germany:

- PNI – Testing Laboratory for Grid Integration
- Mobile UVRT/ OVRT Testing Equipment
- HST – Hybrid System Test Field
- TPE – Test Center for Electromobility with PHIL test setup
- EMA – Electrical Machines Laboratory

Achievements and learning outcomes

The main outcome of the virtual lab tour was to provide a brief overview to students in the online Master course WES-online, how different characteristics (grid code compliance, performance, etc.) of DER units and smart grid components could be assessed, validated and demonstrated in a lab infrastructure.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Statistics of the event (Webinars or Virtual Workshops)

Statistics of the virtual lab tour:

- No. Registered persons: 19
- No. of Attended Persons: 13
- No. of Project External Persons: 11

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.5.3 Lecture on advanced real-time supervision and centralised control of distributed energy resources in smart grids

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Report

Advanced real-time supervision and centralized control of distributed energy resources in smart grids

Overview

Hosting partner: University of Cyprus (UCY) - FOSS Research Centre for Sustainable Energy

Co-organizing partners: -

Delivered date: 31st October 2021

Type of Activity: Seminar

Contact: George Makrides (makrides.georgios@ucy.ac.cy)

Agenda and Schedule of the event

The schedule shared for the online seminar is provided below.

14:00	14:10	0:10	Welcome by Dr George Makrides <i>Senior Researcher (University of Cyprus)</i>
14:10	15:00	0:50	Advanced real-time supervision and centralized control of distributed energy resources (DERs) in smart grids <i>Seminar presentation by Dr George Makrides (University of Cyprus)</i>
15:00	15:15	0:15	Closing Remarks, Questions and Discussion

List of participants (Only for Summer/Winter schools and workshops)

A list of participants was not provided since this was an online seminar.

Short description of the event activities/ Presented topics of the event

The seminar focused on equipping participants with in-depth knowledge and practical skills in smart grid interoperability frameworks, DER flexibility, data information models, and the implementation of real-time supervision and control systems. A key highlight of the training was the demonstration of a centralized real-time supervision and control system at a nanogrid pilot, providing participants with hands-on exposure to advanced grid solutions.

The main topics presented include:

- Smart grid interoperability frameworks and DER flexibility - Participants were introduced to the concepts of interoperability frameworks, emphasizing their role in integrating DERs into

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

modern grid environments. The session also explored DER flexibility functions, showcasing how these resources can adapt to dynamic grid demands while maintaining stability and efficiency.

- Data information models for smart inverters - This segment detailed the setup and configuration of data information models for smart inverters, focusing on open communication protocols and standards. Participants learned about standard frameworks such as the SunSpec protocol, gaining insights into how these models enable seamless communication and data exchange between grid components.
- Programmable automation devices and interoperability - Attendees were demonstrated the process to configure programmable automation devices to establish connections with specific registers of smart inverters. This hands-on activity highlighted the practical implementation of interoperability protocols, ensuring real-time data acquisition and command execution in smart grid operations.

Overall, the seminar empowered attendees with both theoretical knowledge and practical skills, positioning them to contribute effectively to the development and management of advanced smart grid solutions.

Achievements and learning outcomes

The seminar achieved significant milestones (main achievements) in:

- Advancing knowledge and practical understanding of real-time supervision and centralized control of distributed energy resources (DER) in smart grids.
- Introducing key concepts of smart inverter controls and interoperability protocols, enhancing their ability to integrate and manage DER assets effectively.
- Illustrating the architecture of cloud-based supervision systems, providing insights into how these systems optimize the monitoring and control of DERs in modern grid environments.

The participants completing the seminar gained the skills to:

- Design data information models tailored for smart inverter supervision and control.
- Enhance knowledge for the development of interoperability interfaces and validate the functionality of programmable automation devices for efficient DER management.
- Acquire a comprehensive understanding of the configuration structures underlying smart grid solutions, enabling them to perform real-time supervision and control of interconnected inverter-based technologies.
- Validate smart grid asset digitalization and controls for real-time observability.
- Demonstrate novel grid-edge controllers and cloud-based tools for real-time supervision and control.

Statistics of the event (Webinars or Virtual Workshops)

The seminar was attended by:

- No. of Attended Persons: 6 people (all external to ERIGRID 2.0 project).

The photo of the event (online seminar) is provided below.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Tutorial
31 October, 2021
© The ERIGRID 2.0 Consortium
EU Horizon 2020 Programme Grant No. 870620

Figure 1: Photo of online seminar.

Feedback from participants (For activities that distributed questionnaires to participants)
A questionnaire was not distributed at the end of the seminar.

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.5.4 Video: Construction of small WT

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan

Construction Video of a Locally Manufactured Small Wind Turbine

Overview

Hosting partner: ICCS-NTUA

Co-organizing partners: N/A

Planned date (approximate): Summer 2023

Type of Activity: Video

Contact: Kostas Latoufis, latoufis@power.ece.ntua.gr

Short Description

A description of the selection of topics, the hosting partners, intended audience and why the course is relevant to ERIGrid 2.0

A video which describes the manufacturing process of a 2.4m rotor diameter small wind turbine has been filmed and edited by the ICCS-NTUA. The video describes in detail the manufacturing of the wooden blades and hub, of the generator stator and coils, of the generator rotor and magnets, of the metal support frame, and of the tail boom and vane.

The audience of the video is members of the [Wind Empowerment](#) network, and all local manufacturers of residential small wind turbines. Wind Empowerment consists of more than 50 member organisations on all continents, such as cooperatives, collectives, enterprises, non-governmental organisations, research groups, universities, institutions, training centres, as well as hundreds of individual practitioners around the world.

This video supports the development of locally manufactured small wind turbines, thus accelerating the validation and deployment of novel technologies, which is part of the ERIGrid 2.0 agenda.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

Why is this training activity required? What specific outcomes of EG-2 are conveyed here?

Link to appropriate studies, directives, project ambition, etc.

About one billion people today don't have access to grid electricity, and small-scale renewable energy systems can empower rural communities to generate electricity from locally available resources offering

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

opportunities for improved and sustainable livelihoods. Locally manufactured small wind turbines contribute to this direction, often complementing other renewable energy technologies in small-scale hybrid systems. In addition, locally manufactured small wind turbines, as parts of renewable energy systems, offer electrification and decarbonisation services, as required for a net-zero future while meeting the relevant Sustainable Development Goals of the UN. While research is conducted in these fields at the ICCS-NTUA, thus supporting various aspects of these ambitions, it is also necessary to develop educational tools to facilitate the empowerment of citizens in the renewable energy transition. This educational video on how to manufacture locally a small wind turbine, aims at developing such perspectives.

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

As Training Objectives Describe the competences that should be conveyed to the learners in your technical perspective.

This video intends to:

- Introduce viewers to small scale renewable energy applications, such as residential small wind turbines.
- Assist viewers in the manufacturing of a residential small wind turbines.
- Highlight the challenges involved with the local manufacturing of small wind turbines.
- Provide a link between the experiential learning of a manufacturing workshop and online resources on the topic.

In addition, try to specify the expected learning outcome as “Intended Learning Objectives” – specific measurable abilities that the course is intended to convey. We will use Bloom’s revised taxonomy to describe the school’s objective – Appendix 1 has an illustration to reference

A viewer who has watched this video is able to:

1. Comprehend how to organize a small wind turbine manufacturing project (materials, tools, space required).
2. Reproduce on their own part or the complete manufacturing process.
3. Evaluate the results of their manufacturing activities.

Outline of Training Activity

Describe here the key components and learning activities comprising the training activity. A time schedule can be included here if available.

N/A

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Evaluation approach

How is the success of the training activity evaluated? Note EG-2 requests an evaluation only by the organizers (NA3-Training_Activity_Report_Form)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.6 Activity Plan Forms for Modules and Hands-on Lab Education

A.6.1 Lab Module: Conformance test procedures for PV inverters

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan Conformance Test Procedures for PV Inverters

Overview

Hosting partner: CRES

Co-organizing partners: N/A

Planned date (approximate): October 2023

Type of Activity: Laboratory Module

Contact: Evangelos Rikos, vrikos@cres.gr

Short Description

A description of the selection of topics, the hosting partners, intended audience and why the course is relevant to ERIGrid 2.0

The module is a guideline document that describes the required hardware (H/W) setup and testing procedures towards pre-standardization of PV inverters.

The relevance of the specific module to the ERIGrid 2.0 activities arises from two aspects: Firstly, the scenarios investigated by ERIGrid 2.0 include, to a large extent, integration of DER units into distribution grids. One particular type, namely PVs is a predominant technology and, as such, the inverters for this technology should comply with specific norms. As a pre-standardization procedure, the specific guideline provides some useful insights and familiarizes the user with specific requirements for these tests that can be used either for direct testing of commercial products or designing and prototyping of new ones.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

Why is this training activity required? What specific outcomes of EG-2 are conveyed here?

Link to appropriate studies, directives, project ambition, etc.

This module is useful as part of the ERIGrid 2.0 activities connected to TA, JRA and NA work packages. It is particularly relevant to understanding the Holistic Test Case description as it provides a summary and a first step towards the description of a detailed set of testing procedures, since it includes aspects ranging from the purpose of investigation to the H/W setup and indicative results expected from each test. It is also relevant to other activities related to the JRAs and specifically uncertainty representation and identification. As an experimental procedure description, it is also relevant to TA activities especially to projects related to conformance tests.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

As Training Objectives Describe the competences that should be conveyed to the learners in your technical perspective.

This module intends to familiarize users with two aspects:

- Understanding the operating requirements for PV inverters,
- Preparing and conducting preliminary evaluation experiments relevant to standardized tests for PV inverters.

In addition, try to specify the expected learning outcome as “Intended Learning Objectives” – specific measurable abilities that the course is intended to convey. We will use Bloom’s revised taxonomy to describe the school’s objective – Appendix 1 has an illustration to reference

A student who completed this course can:

1. Understand operating characteristics and requirements for PV inverters
2. Understand and implement the procedures that help conduct various pre-standardization tests for the PV inverters.

Outline of Training Activity

Describe here the key components and learning activities comprising the training activity. A time schedule can be included here if available.

The module exists in the form of a document that describes the experimental setup required and expected results towards evaluating the conformance of PV inverters with specific grid norms.

The description provided in this document includes a number of tests categorized in three major groups, namely performance, interference and protection tests. All these tests combined provide the user with a better overview regarding the complete set of requirements that a commercial PV should meet to be used with the grid. This insight can be useful in multiple ways to enable different approaches by the user. For instance, it can be used in order to verify the operating characteristics of a commercial, off-the-shelf product. Alternatively, it can be used for designing and prototyping purposes such as of an inverter either as a H/W prototype or S/W implementation as part of a simulation model. For better understanding of the procedures the document provides examples of the related H/W setups as well as exemplary test results that are expected from each test. One such example is illustrated in the following diagrams. This test involves the validation of the inverter’s protection against leakage current at the DC side and apart from the H/W setup that one could use to assess this functionality a set of measurements is also provided that indicate the response times of the protection activation in various scenarios.

Other tests described in the document include the Maximum Power Point and Efficiency performance, Harmonics and DC current injection as well as the response to Voltage/frequency protection.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Evaluation approach

How is the success of the training activity evaluated? Note EG-2 requests an evaluation only by the organizers (NA3-Training_Activity_Report_Form)

The success of the module could be evaluated by the number of users/downloads of the document.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.6.2 Lab Module: Primary and secondary control techniques in inverter dominated microgrids using real-time digital simulation

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan

Primary and secondary control techniques in inverter dominated microgrids using real-time digital simulation

Overview

Hosting partner: ICCS-NTUA

Co-organizing partners:

Planned date: 1/2024

Type of Activity: Laboratory module

Contact: Alkistis Kontou (alkistiskont@gmail.com)

Short Description

The exercise aims to familiarize participants with the fundamental concepts of inverter-based microgrids and to develop an understanding through real-time digital simulation of the following primary and secondary control techniques/algorithms:

- Conventional Droop Control
- Generalized Droop Control
- Centralized Secondary Control
- Distributed Level Averaging PI Secondary Control

Additionally, the exercise aims to provide hands-on simulation experience using the RTDS real-time simulator and intuitive insight into the concept of design trade-offs, which is an integral part of an engineer's daily practice.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

The aim is to familiarize students, young researchers and professionals with the concept of smart grids and the use of advanced laboratory tools for testing and validation purposes.

Target group(s)

Undergraduate and PhD students, you researchers and professionals.

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

The lab module is designed to:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

- **Recall and understand** the fundamental concepts of inverter-based microgrids.
- **Analyze** the role and importance of microgrid control layers, particularly in islanded operation.
- **Apply and evaluate** the principles governing conventional and generalized droop control through hands-on simulation experience.
- **Analyze and evaluate** the impact of centralized secondary control and distributed average-based secondary control on system behavior through practical simulation experience.
- **Synthesize and create** conclusions by identifying trade-offs in control system design, recognizing how different parameters influence decisions, and understanding that the optimal choice may vary depending on the specific application.

A student who completed this course is able to:

- Recall the basic concepts of microgrids with inverters.
- Grasp the role and importance of microgrid control levels and distinguish between them.
- Design and apply primary control of inverters (droop control)
- Design and apply centralized secondary control of microgrids
- Design and apply distributed secondary control of microgrids

Outline of Training Activity

The lab module includes a preparatory component where students are introduced to the theoretical concepts necessary for completing the lab activities. This preparatory material can be delivered in a lecture format and corresponds to the content outlined in Section 3.2 (“Theoretical background of the exercise – Control layers and techniques in inverter-based microgrids”). It is recommended to focus on Subsections 3.2.1, 3.2.2, 3.2.5, 3.2.6, and 3.2.7, while Subsections 3.2.3 and 3.2.4 may be briefly covered for completeness. The objective of this module is to ensure students can recall foundational concepts and explain them, demonstrating a solid understanding of the material.

The lab module is structured into three sections:

- Primary Control (11 tasks)
- Centralized Secondary Control (3 tasks)
- Distributed Average-Based Secondary Control (10 tasks)

The tasks within the lab are categorized according to their learning objectives:

- **Execution Tasks:** Students will apply theoretical knowledge by conducting simulations with varying parameters, utilizing key theoretical equations to validate measurement results, and designing qualitative diagrams.
- **Analysis and Commentary Tasks:** Students will analyze and evaluate the influence of different parameters on overall system performance based on their simulation outcomes, making connections between concepts and providing insightful commentary on their observations.

This lab module aims to bridge theoretical knowledge with hands-on experience, reinforcing learning through simulation-based experimentation and critical reflection.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Evaluation approach

How is the success of the training activity evaluated? Note EG-2 requests an evaluation only by the organizers (NA3-Training_Activity_Report_Form)

- To evaluate students' depth of understanding, their overall performance in completing the various tasks will be assessed and a grade will be provided.
- A questionnaire can be distributed to the learners.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Appendix B: Activity Reports

B.1 Template for Activity Report Form

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Report

<Title>

Overview

Hosting partner:

Co-organizing partners:

Delivered date:

Type of Activity: *select one of:* Workshops or Seminars (including virtual interactive workshops); Training Schools (Fill-in the additional fields!); Tutorials (e.g. in context of a conference); Special sessions and Panel Sessions; Training of Professionals; Training of High School Students

Contact: Name, email address of person(s) filling in this form

Agenda and Schedule of the event

Provide the agenda and/or schedule of the event. (The schedule mostly applies to summer/winter schools and workshops)

List of participants (Only for Summer/Winter schools and workshops)

Provide the list of participants.

Short description of the event activities/ Presented topics of the event

Provide information about the educational event, description of each presented topic, whether it was related to an ERIGrid 2.0 workpackage, etc.

Achievements and learning outcomes

Describe the main achievements and outcomes of the event (e.g. the participants familiarized themselves with topic A, etc.)

Statistics of the event (Webinars or Virtual Workshops)

Provide statistics (No. Registered persons, No. of Attended Persons, No. of Project External Persons).

A. *Insert a picture of the event video on YouTube or any other public repository (e.g. Zenodo)*

B. *Insert photos of the event*

Feedback from participants (For activities that distributed questionnaires to participants)

In case a questionnaire was distributed to participants, please provide the results.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Consortium

Disclaimer

All information provided reflects the status of the ERIGrid 2.0 project at the time of writing and may be subject to change.

Neither the ERIGrid 2.0 Consortium as a whole, nor any single party within the ERIGrid 2.0 Consortium warrant that the information contained in this document is capable of use, nor that the use of such information is free from risk. Neither the ERIGrid 2.0 Consortium as a whole, nor any single party within the ERIGrid 2.0 Consortium accepts any liability for loss or damage suffered by any person using the information.

This document does not represent the opinion of the European Community, and the European Community is not responsible for any use that might be made of its content.

Copyright Notice

© 2025 by the authors, the ERIGrid 2.0 consortium. This work is licensed under a "CC BY 4.0" license.

